

Master Thesis in Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

A Multimodal Dataset for Vocal Pedagogy

Suvi Häärä

Supervisor: Raphael Ramirez

August 2024

Contents

List of Figures

List of Tables

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Motivation	1
1.2	Research Questions	2
1.3	Research Objectives	3
1.4	Structure of the Thesis	3
2	Background	4
2.1	Physiology of Singing	4
2.1.1	Singing VS Speech	4
2.1.2	Physiology of Singing	5
2.1.3	Vocal Folds and Laryngeal Muscles	6
2.1.4	Breathing	6
2.1.5	Posture	7
2.1.6	Phonation Modes	7
2.1.7	Onsets	8
2.1.8	Common Challenges for Beginners	8
2.2	State of the Art	9
2.2.1	Audio VS Multimodal Data	9
2.2.2	Existing Vocal Datasets	10
2.2.3	Existing Vocal Training Technologies	12
2.3	Multimodal Feature Extraction	15
2.3.1	Audio Features	15
2.3.2	Video Features	15
2.3.3	Biosignal Data	17
2.4	Summary of Background Research	17
3	Materials and Methods	18
3.1	Data Collection	18
3.1.1	Singer Recruitment	18
3.1.2	Recording Settings	19
3.1.3	Data Collection Procedure	21
3.2	Data Preprocessing	24
3.3	Multimodal Feature Extraction	24
3.3.1	Audio	24

3.3.2	Video	26
3.3.3	Biosignal Data	26
3.4	Dataset Organisation	26
3.5	Multimodal Vocal Technique Classification	27
3.5.1	Feature Selection	29
4	Results	30
4.1	Multimodal Phonation Classification	30
4.1.1	Combined Phonation Model	30
4.1.2	Individual Phonation Model for Participant 14	31
4.1.3	Individual Phonation Model for Participant 9	32
4.2	Building a Model for Crossmodal Vocal Technique Error (VTE) Detection	33
4.2.1	7-way VTE KNN Classifier	33
4.2.2	7-way VTE MLP Classifier	34
4.2.3	7-way VTE Random Forest (RF) Classifier	35
4.2.4	Feature Selection	36
4.2.5	4-way Random Forest VTE Classifier with RFE	37
4.3	Crossmodal VTE Detection	38
4.3.1	Combined VTE Model	38
4.3.2	Individual VTE Model for Participant 14	39
4.3.3	Individual VTE Model for Participant 9	40
4.3.4	Spectrogram-Based Convolutional Neural Network VTE Model	41
5	Discussion and Conclusion	42
5.1	The Multimodal Vocal Dataset	42
5.2	Multimodal Feature Extraction	43
5.3	Phonation Classification Model	43
5.4	Building a System for Crossmodal VTE	45
5.5	VTE Classification Model	46
5.6	Future Research and Development	48
5.7	Conclusion	49
	Bibliography	50
	Appendices	54
	A Links for Reproducing the Work	55
	B Experiment to Verify Electromyography (EMG) Sensor Placement	56
	C Evaluating the Suitability of FLD Libraries	58
	D MediaPipe Pose Landmarks	60
	E Alternate 4-way Classification Models	61
E.1	4-way MLP VTE Classifiers with SelectKBest	61
E.2	Random Forest 4-way VTE Classifiers with SelectKBest	62

Acknowledgement

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to:

My supervisor, Rafael Ramirez, and the entire Music Technology Group of UPF for providing me with an environment to explore my passion for voice technologies. Their guidance and expertise have been invaluable in advancing my knowledge in the field of sound and music computing.

My long-term voice coach from Finland, Mona Castrén, has been an integral part of my journey for years. Her support and guidance have helped me develop a deeper connection with my voice and provided an invaluable introduction to the intricacies of voice pedagogy. I am grateful for her willingness to share her experiences as a voice coach, which greatly contributed to the development of this dataset.

My vocal coach in Spain, Lisbeth Ortega, for her helpful discussions and support throughout this year. Her insights and encouragement have been invaluable in helping me reconnect with my voice, especially after the challenging times of COVID-19, and have helped me navigate both my vocal practice and this project.

Marianne Murtoniemi, a long-term family friend and vocal coach, for insightful discussions that were valuable in developing this dataset.

The countless participants, who I cannot name, but am indebted to. This project would not have been possible without your collaboration.

Finally, my friends and family for their unwavering support and encouragement throughout my academic journey. Their belief in me, even from afar, has been a source of strength and motivation. I am indebted to all of you for your invaluable contributions and support. This achievement would not have been possible without you.

Thank you for being part of this journey with me.

Abstract

The voice is a complex instrument, requiring singers to understand the intricate relationships between physical actions, sensory feedback, and sound production. This complexity presents a unique opportunity to explore how technology can enhance musical learning. Beginners face numerous challenges in singing, including breath control, vocal fold closure, laryngeal positioning, articulation, resonance and posture. Current singing voice datasets are often audio-centric and focus on tasks such as source separation or singer identification, neglecting the physical aspects and missing appropriate labels crucial for developing technologies for vocal pedagogy.

This thesis presents a multimodal dataset designed to address this gap by capturing audio, video, and biosignal data. The dataset was created by recording audio from three sources (a 2017 MacBook Air, an iPhone 14 Pro, and a Behringer C-3 microphone), video from two sources (a 2017 MacBook Air and an iPhone 14 Pro), an electromyography sensor and a piezoelectric respiration sensor. We collected data from 14 participants, including professional, intermediate, and inexperienced singers, who sang various scales to ensure variability in vowel sounds, note lengths, and pitches.

We developed Python scripts and Jupyter Notebooks, available on GitHub, for data alignment and cleaning¹, feature extraction², and the development of various machine learning models³. We compared K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN), Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), and Random Forest (RF) classifier architectures to determine the most effective models, modalities and features for classifying phonation and vocal technique errors (VTEs). Individual models for two participants, a combined model, and their results were compared to identify the most relevant features for vocal pedagogical applications.

Our results demonstrate the dataset's effectiveness in phonation and VTE classification. A 2-way phonation KNN classifier achieved approximately 75% accuracy with

¹https://github.com/suvimh/vocal_data_cleaning

²https://github.com/suvimh/vocal_data_feature_extraction

³https://github.com/suvimh/vocal_data_feature_based_classification_for_colab

both individual and combined data models using 5 features. The optimal approach for crossmodal VTE classification was a set of six 2-way RF models using Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE), which achieved average accuracies of around 71% with only five features.

This research advances vocal pedagogical technologies by providing a multimodal dataset that includes audio, video, and biosignal data, capturing both expressive resources and vocal technique errors. Future work should focus on developing a generalised model that personalises feedback as it learns from individual users' voices. Such a system could start with a general model and progressively refine its feedback with user-specific data.

The code and resources developed for this study are available on GitHub, facilitating further research and reproducibility.

Keywords: Vocal Pedagogy; Machine Learning; Multimodal Data; Crossmodal Analysis; Music Technology; Sound and Music Computing

List of Figures

1	Human Physiology for Singing	5
2	Representation of the Differences Between Phonation Modes	8
3	The Yousician UI for Singing	13
4	SING&SEE User Interface	14
5	FONASKEIN User Interface	14
6	The Skynote UI for Violin	14
7	List of Features Identified by Girado et al.	15
8	Sex and Age Distribution of the Participants	19
9	Diagram of the Equipment Setup for Data Collection	20
10	PZT Sensor and Its Placement	20
11	EMG Sensor and Its Placement	21
12	Flowchart of Data Collection Procedure	22
13	Summary of Dataset Structure	26
14	Confusion Matrices for VTE KNN classifiers	34
15	Confusion Matrices for VTE MLP classifiers	34
16	Confusion Matrices for VTE RF Classifiers	35
17	Feature Count vs. Accuracy for SelectKBest and RFE	37
18	Accuracies of 2-Way Phonation KNN Classifier Models	44
19	Accuracies of the VTE Models in this Thesis	45
20	Accuracies of 2-Way VTE Models RF Classifiers with RFE	47
21	Data Output When Singing the Exercise 'ngi-nge-nga-o-u'	56
22	Data Output When Singing a Siren Exercise	57
23	Screen Shots from Qualitative FLD Assessment	58
24	Confusion Matrices for Posture VTE RF Classifiers	62
25	Confusion Matrices for Other VTE RF Classifiers	63

List of Tables

1	Summary of Existing Voice Datasets	10
2	Summary of Some Popular Human Pose Estimation Libraries	16
3	Summary of Some Popular Face Landmark Detection Libraries	16
4	Results for KNN Phonation Classification for Combined Data	31
5	Results for KNN Phonation Classification for Participant 14	31
6	Results for KNN Phonation Classification for Participant 9	32
7	Results for 7-way VTE KNN Classifier	33
8	Results for 7-way VTE MLP Classifier	35
9	Results for 7-way VTE Random Forest Classifier	36
10	Feature Selection Algorithms Performance for 7-Way VTE Classification	36
11	Results for 4-way Posture VTE RF Classifier	38
12	Results for 4-way Other VTE RF Classifier	38
13	Results for 2-way VTE RF Classifiers for Combined Data	39
14	Results for 2-way VTE RF Classifiers for Participant 14	40
15	Results for 2-way VTE RF Classifiers for Participant 9	41
16	Results For CNN with Audio Spectrogram Input	41
17	Mediapipe HPE landmark locations	60
18	Summary of Posture MLP Classification Results	61
19	Summary of Other VTE MLP Classification Results	62
20	Summary of Posture RF Classification Results	62
21	Summary of Other Error Condition RF Classification Results	63

Chapter 1

Introduction

The voice is often seen as a complex and mysterious instrument as the physical mechanisms that produce sound are hidden from the listener’s sight. Additionally, for the singer, the interaction with the instrument is highly personal, involving a combination of listening to the sound and feeling internal sensations within the body [1]. To gain command of their instrument, vocalists must develop a deep understanding of the associations between internal physical actions, sensory feedback and the produced sound. A singer must be able to translate between bodily, and linguistic representations of experience, typically rooted in more abstract mental understandings. As the interaction with the voice is largely without a visible physical interface, it isn’t easy to describe the sensation of singing to another person. Vocal coaches have to navigate the challenges caused by the abstract nature of the voice to facilitate learning. Therefore, the voice provides a unique perspective to investigate how technology can assist musical learning.

1.1 Motivation

The motivation for this research stems from various works that highlight the potential of integrating multimodal data into vocal technologies. Firstly, the PhD by Reed at QMUL [1] demonstrated how using biosignal feedback such as electromyography (EMG) can enhance voice technologies. A variety of works such as those by Ephrat et al.[2], Gao et al.[3], Nguyen et al.[4] and Wu et al. [5] show that a combination of multimodal data sources tends to outperform audio-only configurations in speech separation. Similar findings have been made by Montesinos et al. [6] and Li [7] regarding multimodal singing voice separation as well as speech enhancement and separation by Michelsanti et al. [8]. Inspired by these, this thesis addresses the lack of appropriate multimodal data required to develop technologies for vocal pedagogy. While platforms like Yousician ¹ and Skynote [9] show that there is a space for music pedagogical technologies, these platforms are underdeveloped for voice. I believe that the lack of appropriate data is one of the underlying causes of this. A gap appears in creating a multimodal dataset for vocal pedagogy.

¹<https://yousician.com/company>

The implications of this research extend beyond technology to the realm of vocal and musical pedagogy, and could potentially even impact fields such as Human-Computer Interaction (HCI). By collecting biosignal data in addition to audio and video, this thesis provides a means to delve into the intricacies of the internal interactions of vocal practice. This can lead to the development of technologies that allow singers to foster a deeper understanding of the dynamic relationship between their bodies and the act of singing.

On a personal level, my journey as a vocalist motivated this research. I found that the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the limitations of traditional face-to-face vocal training and existing technologies were unsuited to support my practice. This partially motivated my bachelor's research, prompting a reevaluation of alternative methodologies and an exploration of pitch and timbre analysis of the voice. This thesis aims to further said work by forging a path for developing accessible avenues for vocalists to hone their craft in conjunction with conventional lessons.

Voice training can be hindered by miscommunication and anxiety, particularly when there's a disconnect between teachers' and students' ways of thinking. Through technological innovation, there's an opportunity to facilitate clearer communication and understanding between teachers and students, thereby creating a better learning environment.

In essence, this thesis provides a strong basis for creating novel technologies for vocal training practices by presenting a dataset that is tailored for crossmodal voice technique error (VTE) detection. It also provides a strong foundation for future work to enhance our understanding of the voice and its interaction with the body. Through this work, we hope to develop systems that empower singers to optimize their practice routines and nurture a healthy relationship with their voices.

1.2 Research Questions

1. Which modality/modalities are the most relevant when designing technologies for vocal training?
2. How can we utilise machine learning and technology to improve vocal training?
3. What expressive resources are most important to develop as a beginner when starting vocal training?
4. What is "good practice" in vocal training?
5. How can technology support learning basic vocal control?
6. What mistakes do singers commonly make when training?
7. What types of exercises should be included in vocal pedagogy technologies?
8. Can we deduce errors happening while singing in one modality from data of another modality?

1.3 Research Objectives

1. Identify which expressive resources are most important to develop when starting vocal training and how these are used "correctly".
2. Identify what common mistakes need to be spotted by vocal training technologies.
3. Collect a small multimodal dataset for voice using audio, video and biosignal data that captures the identified expressive resources and mistakes.
4. Analyse the collected data to discover which modality/modalities are most useful to consider when creating vocal training technologies.
5. Develop a dataset and models from it that could be integrated into Skynote in the future and/or inform its development for voice.
6. Investigate whether mistakes made in one modality could be identified purely from data of another modality.

1.4 Structure of the Thesis

This paper is structured as follows:

Chapter 2 provides foundational background knowledge, including a discussion on the physiology of the voice, an overview of current vocal training technologies, and a review of relevant research and datasets in this domain.

Chapter 3 describes the design and structure of the data collection process. It also details the implementation of various machine learning classifiers used to identify the most effective features and modalities for phonation and vocal technique error (VTE) classification in singing.

Chapter 4 presents the experimental results obtained from the implemented models, highlighting how the different modalities perform and what features seem most impactful in their performance.

Chapter 5 offers a discussion of the findings, along with recommendations for future research. The conclusion emphasizes the potential of the dataset and experimental methods for advancing vocal pedagogical technologies that support crossmodal vocal technique analysis. However, it also underscores the need for further investigation into alternative models and the expansion of the dataset to include a broader range of voice types.

Chapter 2

Background

This chapter begins by defining which aspects of human physiology need to be considered when developing technologies for vocal pedagogy through the lens of my personal experience as a singer, discussions I have had with my vocal coaches and further research in Section 2.1. It then continues to outline the current state of the art, in terms of existing datasets and technologies for vocal pedagogy in Section 2.2. Section 2.3 describes technologies that can be used to extract relevant features based on the findings of Section 2.1, while Section 2.4 summarises the findings of this entire chapter.

2.1 Physiology of Singing

2.1.1 Singing VS Speech

While singing and speech are produced by the same physiological structure, they differ from each other. S. Livingstone et. al. [10] observed that singing exhibits longer duration, higher pitch and greater sound intensity than speech. Sundberg [11] outlines how during speech of a normal loudness range, breathing inhalation is active, while exhalation is passive and the volume of the lungs only varies in a small range. In contrast, during singing, a much larger range of lung capacity is used, and both inhalation and exhalation are considered more active [11].

The differences between singing and speech were also highlighted in my discussions with vocal coaches. For example, in singing, the shape of the mouth is usually modified more actively, the movement of the chin is typically greater than in speech and the tongue and lips have to learn to function separately from each other, but in a balanced way.

While in theory speech data could be augmented via means of time and pitch stretching to attain "singing-like" data to work with, there are various subtler perceivable differences in timbre, pitch, intensity, and the physiological formation between singing and speech. Singing introduces unique challenges and complexities that

require specialized datasets for the development of effective technologies for vocal pedagogy.

2.1.2 Physiology of Singing

Sundberg's research [11] on the science of singing provides an extensive in-depth understanding of how the human voice functions and how different aspects of our physiology impact our voice. It is important to understand the underlying physiology of the voice when developing technologies that will be used to support vocal training.

The voice organ, as seen in Figure 1a consists of the breathing apparatus, vocal folds (a.k.a vocal cords, but referred to as vocal folds in alignment with Sundberg's work), and vocal tract [11]. The size of the vocal folds significantly influences a singer's vocal range. Singing can be considered a combination of voiced and unvoiced sounds. Voiced sounds, like vowels, are characterized by harmonics, while unvoiced sounds, including consonants, are associated with noise. The vocal tract, comprising the pharynx and mouth, contributes to sound resonance and articulation of these sounds [11]. A singer must learn to utilize both voiced and unvoiced sounds in various ways.

The vocal tract acts as a resonator that amplifies some harmonics of the voice source while it dampens others [11]. Certain frequencies are resonant while others are dampened depending on the shape of the vocal tract. The shape of the mouth and the positioning of our pharynx impact the length and shape of the vocal tract, impacting the quality of the voice [11]. As each person's physiology is unique, so is the sound of their voice. As physiological states can change, so can an individual's voice. This uniqueness and variation is one of the major challenges posed by the voice when developing technologies for its analysis.

(a) Representation of the Side View Profile of the Voice Organ [11]

(b) Full Musculature Surrounding the Voice Organ [1]

Figure 1: Human Physiology for Singing

2.1.3 Vocal Folds and Laryngeal Muscles

When singing, the sound is generated by the vocal folds acting as the main oscillators. Sundberg [11] showed that they vibrate due to pressure differences in the area below the vocal folds, called the subglottis. A higher subglottic pressure results in higher pitch and volume. However, for "good" singing practice, the loudness and pitch should not be dependent on each other in this way. It is better to skillfully use the muscles that control the vocal folds to stretch them and create pitch variations rather than simply modifying the pitch using pressure variations. Longer, thinner vocal folds result in higher-pitched sounds. The length and thickness of the vocal folds are controlled by laryngeal muscles, especially the cricothyroid muscle [11]. The full musculature controlling singing can be seen in Figure 1b.

Due to their essential role in "correctly" modifying pitch when singing, it is worthwhile to analyse data on the function of the laryngeal muscles when developing technologies for vocal pedagogy.

2.1.4 Breathing

Breathing is fundamental to the proper functioning of the voice organ, and improving vocal technique often involves adjusting breathing habits [11]. Adjusting breathing patterns can resolve many issues related to phonation (see section 2.1.6), as the quality of the voice is influenced by the position of the abdominal wall. Breathing is easier to observe than the internal workings of the larynx and control over breathing relies on the intercostal muscles along the ribcage, the abdominal wall, the pelvic floor and the diaphragm. Often the goal is to gain more space in the abdomen to allow the sound to resonate in the body to attain a fuller tone. Diaphragmatic breathing is particularly important, as it creates space for sound resonance, contributing to a fuller tone. Therefore diaphragmatic breathing techniques are commonly practised.

Proper breathing, combined with good posture, influences the control and maintenance of subglottic pressure, which affects volume and pitch [11]. Increased subglottic pressure typically results in higher volume and pitch, accompanied by increased airflow through the vocal folds. While optimising airflow is recommended during singing, minimizing it must be done carefully to avoid straining the vocal folds. For instance, inexperienced singers may forcefully constrict the vocal folds while increasing subglottic pressure to reduce airflow, a technique that is detrimental to vocal health. Healthy breathing techniques are essential for achieving higher tones and volumes without damaging the voice [11]. Loudness is mainly controlled by subglottic pressure, while pitch should be regulated by the laryngeal muscles. Singing requires diaphragmatic breathing, engaging the lower abdomen and back, rather than the chest breathing used in everyday tasks.

Given the fundamental role of breathing in vocal production, any system designed to teach singing must focus on helping learners develop healthy breathing habits.

2.1.5 Posture

It is widely accepted among professional singers and vocal coaches that there is a relationship between a singer's posture and voice quality [12]. This was evident in my discussions with vocal coaches, who noted that beginners often struggle to find the correct posture when starting voice training.

Good singing technique usually involves keeping the body loose and relaxed while actively using muscles to support vocalizing. A paper by Luck et. al. on the ideal singing posture [12] showed that there is a relationship between a singer's posture and vocal performance that can be identified experimentally using methods of inverse kinematics. However, analyzing posture is challenging because the issues are often unique to each singer, though basic guidelines can be taught. These include a straight but not overextended back, relaxed shoulders, an open chest, a slightly activated lower back, unlocked knees, and a slight forward rotation ("tucking") of the hips.

Given its impact on sound quality, analyzing posture is important when developing technologies for vocal pedagogy.

2.1.6 Phonation Modes

As stated before, when singing, the sound is generated by the vibrating vocal folds. This is called phonation. Sundberg [11] defines four phonation modes that are defined by the subglottal pressure and glottal airflow used: Neutral, Breathy, Pressed, and Flow, as shown in Figure 2. All phonation modes are used as expressive resources in singing.

Breathy phonation (also called leaky phonation) is the result of air escaping between the vocal folds and results in high air consumption. It is characterized by high airflow and low subglottic pressure [11].

Neutral phonation is characterized by less airflow than breathy phonation and low subglottic pressure, which is slightly higher than in breathy phonation [11]. In neutral phonation, the vocal folds come together evenly and efficiently without excessive tension, resulting in a clear, resonant, and well-supported sound. Neutral phonation is commonly heard in classical singing, musical theatre and contemporary styles when a clean, pure tone is desired. These styles often also use flow phonation, which is considered the most optimised condition in terms of airflow.

Flow phonation involves high subglottic pressure and high airflow [13]. In flow phonation, there may be a slightly more relaxed quality to the vocal folds, allowing for a smoother, more legato sound. While it can be challenging to distinguish between neutral and flow, the tone in flow phonation may have a slightly softer, gentler quality compared to neutral phonation and is typically used for expressive purposes. There may be a subtle airiness present in the sound, particularly at the onset or release of notes.

Figure 2: Representation of the Differences Between Phonation Modes

Pressed phonation involves higher subglottic pressure and lower airflow and can be perceived as a strained voice [11]. A pressed phonation is generally not desirable as it can lead to strain, fatigue, and potential vocal damage. Instead, singers often aim for neutral or flow phonation, where the vocal folds come together evenly and efficiently, allowing for a clear and resonant tone. Breathy phonation, where there is a controlled release of air between the vocal folds, is sometimes used for emotional expression or stylistic effect. Singers need to find a balance between vocal control and expression, using techniques such as breath support and proper vocal placement to achieve their desired sound without causing harm to their voices.

2.1.7 Onsets

Vocal onsets play a crucial role in phonation, representing the initiation of vocalizing. They are closely linked to different phonation modes and significantly influence the quality and characteristics of the produced sound. Glottal onset refers to the sudden closure of the vocal folds without airflow, resulting in a sharp and clear onset of phonation. In contrast, breathy onset occurs when air passes through the vocal folds before they fully close, producing an airy sound at the beginning of phonation. In a third onset type, airflow and vocal fold closure occur simultaneously. These distinct onset types have distinct perceptual qualities and are important considerations in vocal training and voice production techniques.

2.1.8 Common Challenges for Beginners

To develop a better understanding of common challenges that beginners face when singing, I contacted my prior and current vocal coaches. Through my discussions with three vocal coaches, I identified the following key challenges faced by beginners when they start vocal training:

- **Breathing Technique:** Mastering proper breathing technique is fundamental for singing. Beginners should focus on deep, controlled breathing, avoiding

shallow breaths or over-breathing. Engaging in breathing exercises and utilizing tools such as semi-occluded vocal tract exercises can aid in developing breath control and muscle activation.

- **Vocal Fold Closure:** Achieving optimal vocal fold closure is essential for producing clear and resonant tones. Beginners should practice exercises aimed at strengthening vocal folds and coordinating airflow to improve vocal fold closure and control.
- **Articulation:** Clear articulation is crucial for conveying lyrics effectively. Beginners may benefit from exercises targeting tongue and lip activation, as well as jaw flexibility. Practising vowel sounds and tongue placement exercises can help improve articulation skills.
- **Posture:** Maintaining proper posture is vital for optimal vocal production. Beginners should focus on standing with knees slightly bent, maintaining a raised but relaxed stance, and keeping the neck and face muscles free from tension. Good posture facilitates balanced breathing and supports the projection of sound.
- **Resonance and Articulation:** Achieving resonance and clarity in singing requires proper mouth placement and articulation. Beginners should focus on opening the mouth, projecting sound forward, and articulating lyrics clearly.
- **Transitioning Between Registers:** Navigating between different vocal registers can be challenging for beginners. Practice exercises aimed at developing smooth transitions and maintaining vocal connection can help overcome these challenges.
- **Laryngeal Position:** Maintaining the correct laryngeal position is crucial for vocal health and tone quality. Awareness exercises focusing on laryngeal position and relaxation techniques can promote vocal freedom and resonance.

By focusing on these key points when creating technologies for vocal pedagogy, systems could help beginners develop a strong foundation for their practice.

2.2 State of the Art

2.2.1 Audio VS Multimodal Data

The combination of audiovisual information has been shown to outperform audio-only configurations in speech separation tasks such as Ephrat et al.'s speaker-independent audiovisual model for speech separation [2], Gao and Grauman's work on audiovisual speech separation with crossmodal consistency [3], Nguyen et al.'s deep variational generative models for audiovisual speech separation [4], and Wu et al.'s research in time domain audiovisual speech separation [5]. This has also been reflected in the work of Montesinos et al. on audiovisual singing voice separation

[6] and Li’s work on multimodal analysis of music performances [7]. Michelsanto et al. [8] provides an extensive overview of deep-learning-based audiovisual speech separation research. Multimodal approaches have also shown improved performance in singing voice transcription tasks [14] and raga classification tasks [15] when combining audio with other modalities.

2.2.2 Existing Vocal Datasets

While various voice datasets exist, most are audio-focused and tailored to specific tasks unrelated to vocal pedagogy. Table 1 provides a summary of different openly available voice datasets, adapted and extended from the works of Deng et al. [10] and Chowdhury et al. [16]. A significant challenge in developing voice training technologies is the lack of suitable data for evaluation. Many datasets emphasize singer identification rather than the technical aspects of singing styles or the qualities necessary for evaluating vocal performance. Vocalset [17] is an exception but is limited to audio data only.

Singing datasets often suffer from limitations such as a small number of singers, lack of coverage of diverse vocal techniques, skill levels, and absence of musical context [17]. These datasets typically lack labels indicating the quality of performance, technical mistakes or the progress made by individuals between recordings. Additionally, singing datasets are often recorded in soundproofed environments using high-quality microphones, which may not be representative of real-world data. For vocal pedagogical technologies to be effective, they require data that mirrors the conditions in which users would practice, such as at home, and provides insights into vocal training progress and sound quality.

While certain notable datasets, like the Million Song Dataset [18], developed for song recognition, are explored when developing datasets for singing source separation tasks, as done by Chowdhury et al. [16], these datasets are not well suited for the development of vocal pedagogical technologies and therefore are not explored as part of this thesis.

Table 1: Summary of Existing Voice Datasets

Dataset	Number of Samples	Number of Voices	Audio	Video	Biosignal data	Raw Audio	Clean	Labels
UT-Sing [19]	165	33	Yes	No	No	Yes	?	singer
Vocal92 [10]	4456	92	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	singer, sex, age, language
JukeBox [16]	7000	936	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	singer, sex, language
Artist20 [20]	1413	20	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	artist/group
Singing Voice Dataset [21] [10]	Unknown	28	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	singer
A Cappella [6]	1493	Unknown/1493	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	singer, language, gender
URSing Dataset [7] [22]	767	767	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	?	mouth regions
VocalSet [17]	3560	20	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	singer, sex, vocal technique
Phonation Modes Dataset [23]	900	1	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	phonation mode, vowel
Vocobox [24]	Unknown	1	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	note
N20EM [25]	5116 (utterances)	30	Yes	Yes	No	Unknown	Unknown	lyrics

Vocal92

Vocal92 [10] is a multivariate a cappella solo singing and speech audio dataset containing about 147 hours of data sourced from 92 volunteer amateur singers in Chinese and English. The dataset is openly accessible for use free of charge. The data is

labelled with singer, gender, age and language and was developed for singer identification and song conversion tasks.

Artist20

The Artist20 dataset [20] contains 1413 songs from different albums by American and European pop music groups or artists, and is publicly available upon request. The labels in the dataset are associated with the artists or groups rather than individual singers meaning features can vary considerably [10]. It is best suited for artist recognition tasks.

JukeBox

The JukeBox dataset [16] contains about 467 hours of sampled multilingual singing audio data downloaded from the Internet Archive. It is openly available. The data compasses 936 different singers singing in 18 different languages, of whom 533 are male. The data is labelled with singer, gender and language labels for developing and evaluating singer recognition tasks.

The singing voice dataset

The singing voice dataset contains 70 recordings performed by 28 professional, semi-professional and amateur Chinese opera singers [21]. As the dataset is very small, it can typically only be used for testing, not development [10].

A cappella

A Cappella is a publicly available audiovisual a cappella singing dataset containing 46 hours of solo singing videos sourced from YouTube [6]. It was developed for singing source separation.

URSing

The URSing dataset [22] is publicly available. It consists of 65 songs (4 hours) of audiovisual recordings of University of Rochester students singing various songs [7]. It was developed for singing source separation.

VocalSet

Vocalset [17] is a clean singing voice dataset that consists of approximately 10 hours of monophonic recordings of professional vocalists using 17 different techniques on 5 vowel sounds sung as scales, arpeggios, long tones, and excerpts. It contains recordings from 9 male and 11 female vocalists with a range of voice types. It was developed for singer identification, vocal technique identification, and singing generation among other tasks. The audio was only recorded using a studio-quality microphone [17], which might make systems using the data for training less robust to variations in the audio input quality. The paper introducing the dataset also shows examples of how it can be used for vocal technique classification and singer

identification tasks [17]. Although VocalSet is currently the best-suited dataset for vocal pedagogical tasks, it focuses on singing techniques sung by professionals rather than issues beginners typically face.

Phonation Modes Dataset

The Phonation Modes Dataset [23] consists of a range of vocal sounds based on the four different phonation modes from Sundberg’s work: Neutral, Breathy, Pressed, and Flow [11]. The dataset contains a large number of sustained, sung vowel sounds of pitches between A3 and G5 from one female singer. It lacks musical context, as the pitches are isolated and not defined in e.g. a scale or arpeggio. The dataset focuses on the way that the sound is shaped by the different formations of the throat, without any focus on the musical applications of the techniques [17].

Vocobox

Similar to the Phonation Modes Dataset, the Vocobox dataset [24] only contains recordings from one singer. It consists of recordings of single vowel and consonant sounds without musical context. Therefore it is not well suited for vocal pedagogical tasks.

N20EM

The N20EM [25] dataset is publicly accessible on request. It consists of a total of 5 hours and 23 minutes of data, 5116 utterances from 17 male and 13 female participants with a range of musical experience [25]. They collected audio, video and IMU (inertial measurement unit) sensor data to record the kinesthetic activity of the head, jaw and lips. The labels contain information about the lyrics rather than information regarding vocal performance techniques.

2.2.3 Existing Vocal Training Technologies

To better understand whether multimodal data is utilised in applications for singing learning, this section briefly outlines the state of existing technologies for vocal pedagogy. In this overview, we’ll examine the strengths and limitations of current technologies while envisioning future advancements that address this crucial aspect of vocal education.

Yousician Singing

Yousician ¹ is an application for music learning across various instruments including guitar, piano, ukulele, bass, and singing. Despite offering a singing learning track, as seen in Figure 3a its development significantly lags behind other instrument tracks, notably guitar. The application relies on audio input and offers some instructional content. However, its effectiveness is limited, as it primarily focuses on pitch tracking while neglecting other critical elements of singing technique. In the singing exercises

¹<https://yousician.com/company>

pitch is displayed to the user, as seen in Figure 3b while other metrics are not present. Consequently, Yousician struggles to provide holistic training in singing, lacking depth in areas beyond pitch correction despite containing video tutorials and breath control exercises.

(a) Yousician provides multiple different kinds of lessons in the singing learning path

(b) When practising, Yousician shows your pitch on screen while presenting the upcoming notes on a piano roll

Figure 3: The Yousician UI for Singing

Sing and See

SING&SEE is a desktop-based voice training application providing comprehensive feedback on vocal performance [26]. Notably, it displays voice alongside piano keys, aiding pitch accuracy assessment with a red dot denoting the current pitch and a blue line tracking pitch transitions. This feature helps users identify pitch overshooting and control vibrato and can be seen in Figure 4. The software also highlights the sung note on a virtual keyboard, facilitating pitch recognition and practice [26].

Additionally, SING&SEE offers a spectrogram display showcasing vocal harmonic content, allowing analysis of timbre [26], also visible in Figure 4. Users can identify characteristics like formant/twang, breathiness, and vibrato from this. However, interpreting spectrograms may challenge many users as they are not intuitive to most people. Users can opt to view only pitch data, the timbral spectrogram, or both simultaneously. Nonetheless, the GUI may appear crowded, hindering users' clarity on vocal qualities [26]. Additionally, SING&SEE relies entirely on audio input for functionality, requiring clear audio signals for accurate feedback and analysis.

FONASKEIN

FONASKEIN [27] is a software application for real-time analysis of the singing voice, primarily focusing on the pitch, as is apparent in Figure 5 which displays the User Interface of the application. Developed in Max/MSP, FONASKEIN features a user-friendly interface with seven distinct windows, emphasizing control over audio input/output and precise vocal tuning via an automatic tuner [27]. While it allows users to explore non-equal tempered scales, and customize scales, it omits analysis of other essential aspects of singing such as tone quality or articulation.

Figure 4: SING&SEE User Interface

Figure 5: FONASKEIN User Interface

Its functionality is solely audio-based, lacking integration with e.g. visual elements that could enhance user experience and analysis comprehensiveness. Despite its strengths, FONASKEIN's narrow focus on pitch and exclusive reliance on audio input may limit its utility for comprehensive vocal analysis.

SkyNote

SkyNote provides real-time feedback on sound quality, timing, pitch accuracy, dynamics, intonation, and gestural technique for various instruments [9]. Through its integration with musical scores and customizable widgets [9], SkyNote enables users to experiment and evaluate their performance. Lessons are displayed as sheet music onto which the pitch contour and other sound quality measures are drawn, as seen in Figure 6a. The platform also has a separate view where users can experiment with their sound quality without a specific melody, as seen in Figure 6b. However, SkyNote is not currently developed for singers, but there is value in developing similar systems to address vocal technique and expression. One of the goals of this thesis is for its findings to inform the development of SkyNote for singers in the future.

(a) Skynote shows your pitch on sheet music

(b) The system also has a separate view that assesses sound quality

Figure 6: The Skynote UI for Violin

2.3 Multimodal Feature Extraction

2.3.1 Audio Features

Girado et al. [28] showed the suitability of feature-based machine learning models in the automatic assessment of tone quality in violin music performance, while Yesiler and Ramirez [29] showed its suitability for singing voice phonation classification. The list of extracted audio features of Girado et al.’s work [28] are listed in Figure 7. Yesiler and Ramirez [29] show merit in analysing alternate features from those identified by Girado et al. for phonation labelling. However, all the features from Girado et al. are implemented in Essentia [30], while those from Yesiler are not. Yesiler et al. used alternate toolboxes to extract their features for phonation classification. SkyNote currently implements the features from Girado et al. using Essentia, which are listed in Figure 7. To align to implement the findings of this study into SkyNote, it would be beneficial to use the same toolboxes and features already implemented in the application.

Feature	Info gain
Pitch	Fundamental frequency in Hz
Energy	Mean Square Root over a 600 ms window
Tristimulus1	Relation of the first fundamental harmonic over the total of harmonic peaks
Tristimulus2	Relation of the second plus the third harmonic peak over the total of harmonic peaks
Tristimulus3	Relation of the remaining harmonic peaks after the third over the total of harmonic peaks
specCent	The spectral center of gravity of the spectrum
specSpread	The spectral standard deviation
specSkew	Measure of the asymmetry of the spectrum around its mean value
specKurt	Measure of the flatness of the spectrum around its mean value
specSlope	Computed from the slope of the linear regression over the spectral amplitude values
specDecr	Averages the set of slopes of the lowest frequencies
specRolloff	Defined as the frequency below which 95% of the signal energy is contained
specFlat	Ratio between the geometric and the arithmetic mean of the spectrum
specCrest	Ratio between the maximum arithmetic mean and the arithmetic mean of the spectrum
MFCC	Mel frequency cepstral coefficients

Figure 7: List of Features Identified by Girado et al. [28]

2.3.2 Video Features

Human Pose Estimation (HPE) Libraries

Due to the essential role of posture in singing, as shown in Section 2.1, it is worthwhile for a vocal pedagogical dataset to contain posture data. This can be attained from video using Human Pose Estimation (HPE).

Chung et al. [31] performed a comparative analysis of four popular state-of-the-art skeleton-based HPE algorithms: OpenPose, PoseNet, MediaPipe Pose and MoveNet. The evaluation of all experiments was based on the percentage of detected joints.

MediaPipe is a machine-learning-based pose estimation solution that uses BlazePose and the ML Kit Pose API to detect up to 33 key points from RGB input in real-time on various devices [31]. Table 2 summarises the specifications of the four HPE libraries [31].

Table 2: Summary of Some Popular Human Pose Estimation Libraries

HPE Libraries	Year Released	Max. Number of Key Points	Key Point Positions on Body	Type of Pose	Method	Underlying Network
OpenPose	2017	135	Face, Hand, Head, Upper Body, Lower Body	Single- and multi-person	Bottom-up	ImageNet with VGG-19
PoseNet	2017	17	Head, Upper Body, Lower Body	Single- and multi-person	Top-down	ResNet and MobileNet
MediaPipe Pose	2020	33	Head, Upper Body, Lower Body	Single-person	Top-down	CNN
MoveNet	2021	17	Head, Upper Body, Lower Body	Single- and multi-person	Bottom-up	MobileNetV2

The study found that while MediaPipe performed poorly with static images, it performed well with videos. It ranked second overall, just 1.38% behind the top performer, MoveNet, and performed the best in 7/14 analysed actions [31]. It is well-suited for tasks where posture analysis does not involve extreme motions, and the priority is on ease of use, especially for real-time applications.

Face Landmark Detection (FLD) Libraries

From Section 2.1, we know that singing requires precise coordination of facial muscles, particularly around the mouth. Ephrat et al. [2] demonstrated that not only the mouth area but also other facial features like the eyes and cheeks enhance the performance of audiovisual speech separation systems. Consequently, including data on facial movements in a vocal pedagogical dataset is valuable. This can be captured from video using Face Landmark Detection (FLD).

Various Python libraries are available for the analysis and extraction of facial landmarks. Prominent among these are libraries such as OpenCV [32], dlib [33], OpenFace [34], and MediaPipe [35]. The features of these four popular Facial Landmark Detection (FLD) libraries are summarized in Table 3. It's important to note that this table provides a focused overview rather than an exhaustive analysis of FLD libraries.

Table 3: Summary of Some Popular Face Landmark Detection Libraries

FLD Libraries	Year Released	Max. Number of Landmarks	Underlying Method
MediaPipe Face	2020	468	CNN
OpenCV	-	-	Contains various solutions
OpenFace	2016	68	DNN
dlib	2002	68	Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG)

Savin et al. compared OpenFace and MediaPipe FLD algorithms for micro-expressions analysis in [36]. They found that MediaPipe, which maps 478 3D face landmarks, outperformed OpenFace in precision. This suggests MediaPipe would be well-suited for detecting facial landmarks for singing, which involves minute control of the facial muscles. However, during data collection, MediaPipe was unable to handle cases when participants turned their heads, as the camera was positioned far enough to capture full-body poses. Due to these limitations, alternative libraries were explored, with dlib ultimately selected for its robustness in handling further distances

combined with head movements. The details of this experiment are summarised in Appendix C.

2.3.3 Biosignal Data

Reed's PhD thesis [1], shows how biosignal data can be leveraged in the development of technologies for voice while section 2.1, outlined the role of breathing and the laryngeal muscles in the quality of singing. Prior research suggests there is merit in including biosignal data in a dataset for vocal pedagogy. Data on breathing can be collected using a piezoelectric respiration (PZT) sensor, while the activity of laryngeal muscles can be detected using a surface electromyography (EMG) sensor, as was used in Reed's PhD thesis. Biosignalsplux [37] provides wearable devices that send data from various biosignal sensors. This includes an EMG sensor designed for high-performance EMG data acquisition under various conditions [38] and a PZT sensor designed for basic respiratory data collection [39].

2.4 Summary of Background Research

One of the key aspects that define the quality of a machine learning model is the quality of its input data. For singing-related tasks, it's crucial to train models with data that accurately captures various aspects of the voice, especially when developing technologies for learning. Existing datasets and technologies, while valuable, often focus solely on auditory feedback and lack the multimodal data and labels necessary for appropriate analysis of the singing voice in the context of vocal pedagogy. This gap, evident in tools like Yousician and Skynote is likely partly due to the lack of appropriate data to develop such systems. Creating a dataset with multimodal data would significantly enhance the development of vocal pedagogy technologies. Leveraging Sundberg's research on vocal physiology [11], a specialized dataset could be used to develop technologies that better identify and address common vocal technique errors (VTEs).

Audio features can be attained using the list of features identified by Girado et al. [28] using Essentia [30]. The physiological aspects of singing can be captured using a combination of video and biosignal data. MediaPipe HPE is well suited for the development of such a dataset due to its strong video performance and usability in real time. Although MediaPipe's detailed FLD with 468 landmarks would be ideal for capturing facial motions during singing, dlib is better suited for a dataset that contains both FLD and HPE data attained from the same camera. dlib allows for a balance between robustness and computational efficiency, while still supporting the exploration of facial landmarks in vocal pedagogy. Biosignal data can be attained using appropriate sensors during data collection.

In summary, advancing vocal pedagogy technologies requires datasets that capture the full range of singing nuances, including physiological aspects. Incorporating multimodal data could transform vocal training by providing deeper insights into the physical processes of singing, presenting a significant opportunity for innovation and motivating this thesis.

Chapter 3

Materials and Methods

This chapter outlines the materials and methods used to create and analyse the multimodal vocal dataset. Section 3.1 describes the methodologies used to acquire the data, including the singer recruitment process, the equipment used and the data collection procedure. Section 3.2 describes how the raw data was preprocessed, while Section 3.3 outlines how various audio and video features were extracted from the raw data. Section 3.4 continues with a brief outline of how the dataset is structured. Section 3.5 describes the various machine learning models used to analyse the data and what feature selection algorithms were considered. Due to time constraints when cleaning the data, the machine learning implementations focused on building individual models for two intermediate female participants. The aim was to find a solution that allowed for the crossmodal vocal technique error (VTE) classification using only audio features from a single source in the data.

3.1 Data Collection

3.1.1 Singer Recruitment

We recruited a diverse participant pool of inexperienced, intermediate, and professional singers to create a small dataset encompassing various skill levels and voice types. An intermediate singer was defined as someone with multiple years of experience in singing, having received several years of individual vocal lessons or participated in a choir for several years. A professional singer was defined as someone actively working in the vocal industry with several years of training and experience. An inexperienced singer was defined as someone without vocal performance or training experience.

The data collection included 14 participants, of whom 2 were professional singers, 5 were intermediate singers, and 7 were inexperienced singers. Among the intermediate singers, 1 had some musical education (1-5 years), while the remaining 4 had significant musical education (over 5 years). Among the inexperienced singers, 1 was self-taught, 5 had some musical experience (1-5 years), and 1 had significant musical

Figure 8: Sex and Age Distribution of the Participants

experience (over 5 years). Musical experience was not solely concerning singing. At the time of data collection, 11 participants still actively practised their instruments, dedicating an average of 7.2 hours per week to this. The ages of the participants ranged from 23 to 35 years, with 5 males and 9 females.

3.1.2 Recording Settings

The individuals were recorded using three separate audio devices to allow for varying types of audio data. All three were used to record audio data, while two of these devices were used to record video. In addition, biosignal data was collected.

2017 MacBook Air

A 2017 MacBook Air with a 720p resolution camera and 30 FPS frame rate was used to record audio and video of the participant. The video was recorded using QuickTime Player and exported as 1280×720 .mov files with stereo audio. During pre-processing, the audio was extracted from the video to enable separate processing of the audio and video data from this source.

iPhone 14 Pro

The camera application of an iPhone 14 Pro was used to record audio and video data of the participants, exported as 1080×1920 p .mov files with stereo audio. During pre-processing, the audio was extracted from the video to allow for separate processing of the audio and video data from this source.

Behringer C-3 microphone

A Behringer C-3 condenser microphone, set to record with a cardioid pattern, was connected to a 2015 MacBook Pro to record higher-quality audio using Logic Pro X. The audio files were recorded in mono and exported as 24-bit mono files with a 44.1 kHz sampling rate, pending further pre-processing.

Figure 9: Diagram of the Equipment Setup for Data Collection

Piezoelectric Respiration (PZT) Sensor

A biosignalsplux piezoelectric respiration sensor (PZT) was used to collect respiration data. As seen in Figure 10b, it consists of a wearable belt containing a sensing element that measures displacement variations caused by the volume changes of the lungs during breathing [39]. This belt was strapped around the diaphragm (just below the lowest rib) on the participants during data collection, as illustrated in Figure 10a. By placing the sensor on the diaphragm, right below the rib cage of the participant as shown in Figure 10a, we aim to represent how diaphragmatic breath varies under different conditions.

(a) PZT Sensor Placement

(b) PZT Sensor [40]

Figure 10: PZT Sensor and Its Placement

Electromyography (EMG) Sensor

A biosignalsplux electromyography (EMG) sensor was used to collect data on the activity of laryngeal muscles. As seen in Figure 11a, it has a bipolar configuration intended for low-noise, medical-grade data acquisition [38]. The sensor is placed on the neck of the participant during data collection, following the EMG sensor placement described by Reed [1], as illustrated in Figure 11b. An experiment was carried out to verify the suitable location to place the EMG sensor, which is documented

in Appendix B. By recording data directly from the muscles involved in singing, we aim to represent the feedback a singer receives internally from their laryngeal muscles in the dataset.

(a) EMG Sensor [41]

(b) EMG Sensor Placement

Figure 11: EMG Sensor and Its Placement

3.1.3 Data Collection Procedure

The data collected for all participants consists of four scales of varying difficulty sung in multiple keys to ensure that the dataset is pitch invariant. The chosen phrases target different vowel sounds, note lengths and intervals. The phrases used are outlined below:

1. **Simple triad scale:** sung using the phrase "ma-me-mi-mo-muu", first ascending in the triad and then descending in the interval pattern 1-3-5-3-1.
2. **Complex vowel scale:** sung using the phrase "ngi-nge-nga-o-u", sung using the interval pattern 1-2-1-3-1-5-3-1. Targets articulation and various vowel sounds.
3. **Sustained phrase:** sung using the phrase "ruu", the aim is to tie all notes together in one sustained sequence, sung using the interval pattern 1-3-5-8-7-5-4-2-1. Most complex of the used scales.
4. **Octave glissando:** sung using the phrase "mm" as a sustained glissando from the reference note to the same note at an octave higher.

First, an example of an exercise was shown to the participant. If needed, this would be repeated until the participant learned the basic scale structure. The reference melody was played on a MIDI keyboard and a sung vocal reference was also provided. The keyboard and vocal references were continued throughout the procedure upon request. Each phrase was repeated multiple times, modulating after each repetition while staying within the range of the participant. Tempo was not targeted. While all participants sang the same four scales, the procedure surrounding this was varied based on their vocal experience level. The full flowchart describing the data collection procedure can be seen in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Flowchart of Data Collection Procedure

Inexperienced Singers

Inexperienced singers first sang the selected phrases without instructions regarding singing techniques to capture their natural singing style. Data collection was then paused to conduct a series of physical and vocal warmups, followed by a short session guiding the participants through basic vocal technique principles. The aim was to have the participants actively think about their posture, breathing, and articulation when singing and to teach them how to prepare their bodies for singing. The exercises, chosen from a variety of those encountered in singing lessons, were specifically aimed at improving diaphragm activation and vocal fold contact. The exercises are summarized below in order of execution:

1. **Tongue root massages:** Alleviating tension in the tongue root and laryngeal muscles.
2. **Stretching:** Releasing tension in the supporting muscles of the lower back and neck.
3. **Checking body posture:** Instructing participants on how to maintain proper singing posture and emphasizing the importance of posture for voice quality.

4. **Basic singing technique:** Guiding participants to check their posture, focus on their breathing before singing, and how to achieve the desired articulation.
5. **Breath and hiss:** Encouraging participants to focus on their breath, breathe into the diaphragm, and maintain diaphragm activation during exhalation.
6. **Siren:** Starting with an 'ng' sound, moving up and down the vocal range to help retain larynx positioning and ensure consistent airflow despite pitch changes. Progressing to a tongue trill (a continuous rolling 'r' sound while varying pitch), and then to a lip trill (a continuous airflow vibrating relaxed lips while varying pitch). These exercises enhance vocal flexibility and control while engaging the diaphragm.
7. **Vocal fry:** Producing a low-pitched, creaky sound by engaging the vocal cords with minimal tension. This exercise helps identify when the vocal folds are in contact, reducing breathiness and generating a fuller sound.

After these warmups and instructions, data was collected as the participants sang through the same sequences as before. This time, additional instructions and reminders about their technique were provided when necessary, emulating the role of a singing teacher in a lesson.

Experienced (Intermediate and Professional) Singers

Experienced singers performed the same phrases, but instead of guiding them through a "singing lesson", they were instructed to deliberately alter their singing posture, breathing, and articulation to be incorrect in various ways. This involved singing with poor posture (hunched, arched, or leaning to either side), breathing only into the chest rather than the diaphragm, hyperarticulating (high articulation) and hypoarticulating (low articulation). Each scenario was documented independently to capture how each incorrect position or technique affected the original sound quality of the participant.

Experienced singers also repeated these conditions while intentionally using a different phonation style. Singers with vocal experience typically use a flow or neutral phonation mode or a combination of both. As discussed in the background research, the differences between these two modes can be very subtle. The participants were also asked to sing using breathy phonation. Pressed phonation data was not collected due to its potential to harm vocal health.

Due to the various conditions to capture with the experienced singer, they were asked to participate in two data collection sessions when possible. Due to time constraints, while each participant recorded conditions in varying phonations, not all 'common mistakes' could be recorded for each experienced participant. However, in most cases, all scenarios were recorded.

3.2 Data Preprocessing

Preprocessing involved manually aligning and cleaning the raw data to obtain the sung phrases from entire singing sessions. A Python Notebook and associated scripts available on Github¹ was developed to handle the alignment and cleaning process of the biosignal data. All data was aligned based on a predetermined alignment point to ensure uniformity across video and audio recordings from the phone, computer, microphone and biosignal dock. Trimming of audio and video was performed using Shotcut video editor. Shotcut and the Python Notebook were used in parallel to isolate the relevant data segments across all mediums.

Silences, talking parts, and other irrelevant segments were removed from the data. Relevant sections of data were exported as individual .mp4 files for video data, .wav files for audio data and a .json file for the biosignal data. The data cleaning procedure also involved checks to ensure that the extracted data ranges included EMG data with high activity as would be expected. Due to the large quantity of data and time restrictions, not all data is fully cleaned at this time.

3.3 Multimodal Feature Extraction

A Python Notebook, available on GitHub² or Google Colab³, was developed for audio and video feature extraction. This notebook also handles the creation of a frame-based multimodal data CSV file, integrating features from audio, and video recordings as well as the biosignal data associated with the frame. Features were extracted for 30ms non-overlapping windows. The alignment of all data frames was based on the time array of the processed microphone audio, as any additional silences identified were further stripped away from the existing recordings. Due to the large quantity of data and time restrictions, the feature extraction procedure was completed only for the data from two intermediate female participants. This data encompassed all recording conditions and two phonation modes: flow and breathy.

3.3.1 Audio

While microphone audio was recorded with a sample rate of 44.1kHz, preprocessing the data using Shotcut resulted in 48kHz .wav files from the microphone. The original audio from both the phone and computer videos was also recorded at 44.1kHz. The audio from these two sources was extracted programmatically after preprocessing with a 44.1kHz sample rate. Loading of all audio for feature extraction was handled by the Essentia Mono Loader. Therefore the stereo audio from the videos was downmixed to mono, so all audio feature analyses were performed on mono audio. The following briefly outlines the various audio features extracted for the frames of each audio source. All features were analysed for a 30ms non-overlapping

¹https://github.com/suvimh/vocal_data_cleaning

²https://github.com/suvimh/vocal_data_feature_extraction

³<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1n0oCDDvmJ6Y0GNAAFF7UNw-SH2JxeegB?usp=sharing>

window and spectral features, using the magnitude spectrum as input. The list of extracted audio features is based on those extracted in the automatic assessment of tone quality in violin music performance by Girado et al. [28] to ensure compatibility with SkyNote.

- **Pitch:** Pitch was extracted using CREPE [42]. As CREPE functions best using longer audio, a pitch curve was generated for the complete audio file which was then sampled to obtain the pitch for each 30ms frame.
- **Note:** Note name of the extracted pitch value for each frame.
- **RMS Energy:** Root Mean Square over the 30ms window.
- **(Spectrum:)** The audio frequency spectrum of the audio.
- **Tristimulus [1, 2, 3]:** The first tristimulus measures the relative weight of the first harmonic [28]. The second tristimulus measures the combined weight of the second, third, and fourth harmonics. The third tristimulus measures the relative weight of the remaining harmonics [28].
- **Spectral Centroid:** A measure indicating where the "center of mass" of the spectrum is, which has a robust connection with the perceived "brightness" of a sound.
- **Spectral Spread:** The variance of the spectrum [28].
- **Spectral Skewness:** Measure of the asymmetry of the spectrum [28].
- **Spectral Kurtosis:** Measure of the "tailedness" of the spectrum [28].
- **Spectral Slope:** Computed from the slope of the linear regression of the spectrum [28].
- **Spectral Decrease:** The decrease of the magnitude spectrum is defined as the linear regression coefficient [28].
- **Spectral Rolloff:** The frequency under which 85% of the total energy of the spectrum is contained (Essentia default).
- **Spectral Flatness:** The ratio between the geometric mean and the arithmetic mean of the spectrum [28].
- **Spectral Crest:** The ratio between the maximum value and the arithmetic mean of the spectrum [28].
- **MFCC FB40:** Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCC) with 40 bands and 13 coefficients (Essentia default).

3.3.2 Video

dlib was used to extract 68 face landmarks, while Mediapipe pose was used to extract 33 body pose landmarks. The videos obtained in the preprocessing step had a frame rate of 25 frames per second. Consequently, the number of video frames was less than the audio and biosignal frames. To ensure proper alignment, the obtained landmarks were copied for all relevant frames in time to synchronize video features with audio features. Video feature extraction was done for both the phone and computer video sources. This process is managed by the code available in the provided GitHub repository³.

3.3.3 Biosignal Data

The dataset contains raw biosignal data without any calculated high-level features. Each row in the CSV contains the raw biosignal data for each 30 ms frame. As the original raw data for the biosignal data contained a data point every 10ms, the feature extraction code programmatically finds the midpoint value of the raw data for a given frame length, essentially resampling the original data. The collected dataset contains PZT, EMG and EEG data, as the EEG data was collected for a separate thesis project conducted in parallel. However, this thesis focuses purely on EMG and PZT biosignal data. While the data from these sensors can be analysed to extract higher-level features, it was decided to focus on the raw data that could be analysed in conjunction with the data from other modalities.

3.4 Dataset Organisation

The final dataset structure is illustrated in Figure 13. As the diagram progresses towards the right-hand side of the figure, all folder structures are replicated for each condition shown on the left-hand side, as denoted by the dotted lines. Variability in the number of clips with different key variations of phrases exists among participants due to varying vocal ranges.

Figure 13: Summary of Dataset Structure

Additionally, the dataset includes a CSV file containing features computed for each file using 30ms non-overlapping windows for those participants' data for which feature extraction has been completed. While most of the data has been cleaned, most awaits feature extraction before it can be used for analysis. The complete raw data

of all participants has been saved and is available separately. The raw data can be reorganised in various ways to allow for different kinds of analysis, such as analyzing entire sessions instead of only clean sung phrases, as desired.

3.5 Multimodal Vocal Technique Classification

A set of Python Jupyter Notebooks, available on GitHub⁴, were used to develop and test various machine learning classification models. These are implemented so that they run within Google Colab. All models were explored thoroughly, comparing the performance when using all data sources, audio only, video only, biosignal only, and audio-video data combined, with all features or performing feature selection and optimisation of up to 5 features. The phonation models were developed for Participants 14, and 9 separately and their combined data. The vocal error detection (VTE) models were first refined using only the data of Participant 14 and the best-performing models were also run with Participant 9's and the combined data. The development of a fully general model awaits the feature extraction of the entire dataset. Explored classification models include:

- **Phonation Modes:** Classification of two different phonation modes present in the data. This was done using a simple K Nearest Neighbour (KNN) classifier, as the classification only involved two classes.
- **Vocal Technique Error (VTE) Detection:**
 - **All VTEs:** 7-way classification of 6 different error conditions and one correct condition present in the data. This was done using a simple KNN classifier, a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) classifier and a Random Forest (RF) classifier.
 - **Posture VTEs:** 4-way classification of 3 conditions with incorrect posture (arched back, hunched back and sideways) and one correct condition present in the data. This was done using a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) classifier and a Random Forest (RF) classifier.
 - **Other VTEs:** 4-way classification of 3 error conditions (chest breathing, high articulation, low articulation) and one correct condition present in the data. This was done using a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) classifier and a Random Forest (RF) classifier.
 - **Separate models for each VTE:** 2-way classification of each error condition (arched back, hunched back, sideways, chest breathing, high articulation, low articulation) and one correct condition. This was done using a Random Forest (RF) classifier.
 - **A brief preliminary test of classification using spectrograms as input and a convolutional neural network:** Instead of using the pre-calculated audio features, the spectrograms of the audio were extracted

⁴https://github.com/suvimh/vocal_data_feature_based_classification_for_colab

from the audio files as images inputted to a Keras Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to classify the different error conditions.

All models were trained on 80% of the data and tested using the remaining 20%. Three main classification models were implemented: a K Nearest Neighbour, a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) and a Random Forest (RF) Classifier. A KNN was selected because it is a straightforward, lightweight model that can work well in real-time classification tasks. MLP was selected, as Furkan [43] showcased its suitability for phonation mode classification using audio features. RF was selected, as it is typically well-suited for multi-class feature-based classification tasks. Finally, a simple CNN architecture using Keras was implemented. Literature shows that CNNs can classify audio based on spectrograms, such as the work of Lee et. al [44], and that of Costa et. al on their suitability for music genre classification [45].

The model parameters for each classifier architecture are summarised below:

- **KNN:** Default scikit-learn `KNeighborsClassifier` [46] parameters with 5 nearest neighbours.
- **MLP:** scikit-learn `MLPClassifier` [47] with hidden layers set as (12,), 0.01 initial learning rate, 0.5 momentum, 2000 maximum iterations, random state of 42, and otherwise using default parameters. Trained with `StratifiedKFold` with 10 splits for cross-validation.
- **RF:** scikit-learn `RandomForestClassifier` [48] with 100 estimators and a 42 random state, otherwise using default parameters. Trained with `StratifiedKFold` with 10 splits for cross-validation.
- **CNN:** Keras Sequential Convolutional Neural Network model [49] with three convolutional layers (32, 64, and 128 filters) followed by max pooling, flattened, and dense layers with dropout for regularization, compiled with Adam optimizer and categorical cross-entropy loss for multi-class classification. Trained with 200 epochs in 32 batches (about 1h of training), with a validation set consisting of 20% of the training data.

The models in this work were trained using only video and audio from the computer, as these would be the primary sources of input when using applications like Skynote. The preprocessing of the full CSV data file was completed using the preprocessing Python Notebook available in the GitHub repository⁴, and can also be viewed in Google Colab⁵.

⁵<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/13BnuW8QTbVA1sq0jKlT8W4QA8TBmRMpi?usp=sharing>

3.5.1 Feature Selection

A maximum of 5 features was selected in the analysis of the different classifier models, as the ultimate goal of the system is to work in real-time and processing an endless amount of features would slow down performance. As one goal was to find which audio features should be used to detect the different VTEs, the various feature selection algorithms were tested on the best-performing machine learning model using only audio features to classify the various error conditions. Due to computational costs, the code was run in Google Colab, using the RF notebook available in the GitHub repository containing the feature classification code³. The notebook can also be viewed within Google Colab⁶. An experiment of different algorithms was carried out to provide insight in which feature selector was best suited for the task. Explored feature selection algorithms include:

- **scikit-learn SelectKBest:** Default feature selection parameters for scikit-learn SelectKBest [50].
- **Correlation-based Feature Selection (CFS):** CFS is a feature selection technique that selects subsets of features with a high correlation with the target label but a low correlation with each other, maximizing information and minimizing redundancy among the selected features [51]. It was implemented in Furkan's thesis [43] for phonation classification of singing, showcasing its suitability for voice-related feature-based classification tasks.
- **Recursive feature elimination (RFE):** RFE feature selection was implemented using the existing scikit-learn RFE function [52] with default configuration and 5 features to select.
- **Recursive feature elimination with cross-validation (RFECV):** RFECV feature selection was implemented using the existing scikit-learn RFECV function [53] with StratifiedKFold cross-validation with 5 folds and accuracy scoring.
- **Principal component analysis (PCA):** PCA was implemented using default parameters of the PCA function in scikit-learn. It transforms the original features into a lower-dimensional space while retaining most of the variance [54].
- **Permutation importance:** Permutation importance quantifies how each feature impacts the model's performance by measuring how the accuracy decreases when the feature values are randomly shuffled[55]. It was implemented using default parameters of the permutation importance function in scikit-learn using default parameters [55].

Finally, the two best-suited feature selectors identified by the preliminary investigation were further tested to acquire a graph displaying how the accuracy of the classifier changed as features were added or removed.

⁶https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1WfXAwKsb7S_KKubDhkPG85D8go7Un0Zk?usp=sharing

Chapter 4

Results

This chapter presents the findings of the thesis. It begins with outlining the results of the multimodal phonation KNN classifier models attained for Participants 14 and 9 separately as well as one using their combined data in Section 4.1. Section 4.2 summarises the results from the various model architectures explored as possible solutions for crossmodal VTE classification. This includes the main KNN, MLP and Random Forest models and the outcomes of feature extraction algorithm experiments. Finally, Section 4.3 outlines the results of the final crossmodal VTE classification Random Forest models attained for Participants 14 and 9 as well as the combined data. This also provides the results of a brief preliminary experiment on using spectrogram images as inputs for a CNN for VTE classification. All the scripts and Python Notebooks are available on GitHub¹.

4.1 Multimodal Phonation Classification

4.1.1 Combined Phonation Model

The Python Notebook containing the run of the KNN Phonation classifier with the combined data can be accessed in Google Colab². The results of phonation classification using the combined data of both Participants 9 and 14 are shown in Table 4. As seen in Table 4, the video modality outperforms other modalities in phonation classification attaining an accuracy of almost 1 and performing well in precision, recall, specificity and false positive rate (FPR). However, audio still performs very well in this task, attaining an accuracy of 77% even when only using 5 audio features for classification. The model using only biosignal data input shows that even simply using the raw biosignal data of the EMG and PZT sensors can indicate the phonation used by the participant, attaining an accuracy of about 55%.

For the models where features were limited, mainly features corresponding to those

¹https://github.com/suvimh/vocal_data_feature_based_classification_for_colab

²https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1HGByimp7wnUagqs-_UIkCofUPSo-BTc?usp=drive_link

Table 4: KNN Classification Results Using Combined Phonation Data

Green values indicate cases where the model accuracy is above 70%, yellow over 60%, while bolded features indicate the selected features also present in Participant 14’s and 9’s models. All the selected video features are from MediaPipe Pose.

Modality	Selected features	Accuracy	F1 score	Precision	Recall	Specificity	False positive rate
All (Mixed Mode)	All	0.9073	0.9072	0.8883	0.9319	0.8826	0.1174
All (Mixed Mode)	MFCC 1, MFCC 3, Left Elbow Z, Right Hip Z, Left Knee Z	0.7783	0.7783	0.7753	0.7841	0.7724	0.2276
Audio Only	All	0.8125	0.8124	0.8288	0.7881	0.837	0.163
Audio Only	RMS Energy, Spectral Slope , Spectral Decrease , MFCC 1 , MFCC 3	0.774	0.774	0.7703	0.7814	0.7666	0.2334
Video Only	All	0.9996	0.9996	0.9998	0.9995	0.9998	0.0002
Video Only	Left Eye Inner Z, Left Shoulder Z , Left Elbow Z, Right Hip Z, Left Knee Z	0.9737	0.9737	0.9741	0.9733	0.9741	0.0259
Biosignal Only	All (raw EMG and PZT)	0.5502	0.5501	0.5491	0.5647	0.5357	0.4643

selected in the models for Participant 14 were selected rather than those of Participant 9. While some video features correspond in joint position, some vary in which 3D point of that point is selected for the classification task.

4.1.2 Individual Phonation Model for Participant 14

The notebook containing the results of the KNN phonation classifier for Participant 14 can be viewed in Google Colab³. The results of phonation classification of Participants 14 are shown in Table 5. As we can see, most metrics improve slightly (between 2-5%) when the model is specific to Participant 14, while some, notably the recall values for the audio and mixed-mode models and all metrics for the biosignal model improve by more than 5%.

Table 5: KNN Classification Results on Participant 14’s Phonation Data

Green values indicate cases where the performance improves from the combined model by more than 5%, yellow by more than 2%, red a decrease in performance, while bolded features indicate which features are also selected in the combined model. All the selected video features are from MediaPipe Pose.

Modality	Selected features	Accuracy	F1 score	Precision	Recall	Specificity	False positive rate
All (Mixed Mode)	All	0.9281	0.9281	0.9107	0.9431	0.9142	0.0858
All (Mixed Mode)	MFCC 1 , MFCC 3 , Left Elbow Y , Right Hip Z , Left Knee Z	0.8146	0.8146	0.7861	0.8445	0.7868	0.2132
Audio Only	All	0.8522	0.8521	0.8515	0.8392	0.8642	0.1358
Audio Only	RMS Energy, Spectral Slope , Spectral Decrease , MFCC 1 , MFCC 3	0.8138	0.8138	0.7856	0.8434	0.7864	0.2136
Video Only	All	0.9999	0.9999	1.0	0.9998	1.0	0.0
Video Only	Mouth Right Y, Left Shoulder Y , Left Elbow Y , Right Hip Z , Left Knee Z	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.0
Biosignal Only	All (raw EMG and PZT)	0.6165	0.6166	0.601	0.6052	0.627	0.373

With audio, MFCCs 1 and 3 contribute the most to classification results using SelectKBest from scikit-learn as the feature selection algorithm, as these are selected

³<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1nlcZX21tvjRkzP9sH0wVY0ovKjwnZ23w?usp=sharing>

in the mixed mode model. The landmarks that contribute the most to phonation classification are the Left Elbow, Right Hip and Left Knee. The audio-only model further selects RMS Energy, Spectral Slope and Spectral Decrease for classifying the phonation of Participant 14. Comparing Table 4 with Table 5, we see that the combined data model mainly selected the same audio and video features for the individual model of Participant 14.

4.1.3 Individual Phonation Model for Participant 9

The Python Notebook containing the run of the KNN Phonation classifier with the data of Participant 9 can be accessed in Google Colab⁴. From Table 6, it can be seen that the results for Participant 9 follow the same general trends as those seen before. When performing 2-way classification of phonation with a KNN classifier, video continues to outperform audio when using the data from Participant 9. However, the models given only audio data still attain good classification accuracy. However, the performance metrics of the audio-only and biosignal-only models are lower when classifying the phonation of Participant 9 than Participant 14. However, the mixed mode model performs better than that of Participant 14 or the combined data. However, the mixed mode only uses video features for classification, unlike the combined data or Participant 14’s model. We can also see that overall, the model performs worse in Participant 9’s individual model than the combined data model for most cases.

Table 6: KNN Classification Results on Participant 9’s Phonation Data

Green values indicate cases where the performance improves from the combined model by more than 5%, yellow by more than 2%, red a decrease in performance, while bolded features indicate which features are selected for both participants’ models. All the selected video features are from MediaPipe Pose.

Modality	Selected features	Accuracy	F1 score	Precision	Recall	Specificity	False positive rate
All (Mixed Mode)	All	0.9602	0.9602	0.9523	0.9725	0.9468	0.0532
All (Mixed Mode)	Right Eye Z, Right Eye Outer Z, Left Ear Z, Mouth Left Z, Left Shoulder Z	0.9626	0.9626	0.9593	0.9694	0.9551	0.0449
Audio Only	All	0.7893	0.7894	0.8088	0.7813	0.798	0.202
Audio Only	Spectral Slope, Spectral Decrease, Tristimulus 1, MFCC 1, MFCC 3	0.7363	0.7363	0.7494	0.7438	0.728	0.272
Video Only	All	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.0
Video Only	Right Eye Z, Right Eye Outer Z, Left Ear Z, Mouth Left Z, Left Shoulder Z	0.9626	0.9626	0.9593	0.9694	0.9551	0.0449
Biosignal Only	All (raw EMG and PZT)	0.5234	0.5227	0.5421	0.5649	0.4781	0.5219

When selecting 5 features using SelectKBest for the data of both participants, Spectral Slope, Spectral decrease, MFCC 1 and MFCC 3 are selected. Only one audio feature varies between the two participants. RMS Energy is selected for Participant 14 while Tristimulus 1 is selected for Participant 9. This is not the case for video mode, as only one selected feature is on the same body part as in the combined model.

⁴https://colab.research.google.com/drive/16Uh_NOE4-2ytciLc_Ixn_J1JvjbNsEnf?usp=sharing

4.2 Building a Model for Crossmodal Vocal Technique Error (VTE) Detection

Vocal Technique Error (VTE) classification was implemented using a KNN, an MLP and an RF classifier. While various versions of these models were experimented with to find the most suitable solution, this section focuses on the main findings. Detailed results can be viewed in the Github⁵ or Google Colab links provided in this section. Only the data from Participant 14 was utilised to find a suitable model architecture.

4.2.1 7-way VTE KNN Classifier

The notebook containing the results of the KNN VTE classifier for Participant 14 can be viewed in Google Colab⁶. As seen in Table 7, video outperforms other modalities in 7-way VTE classification using a KNN classifier attaining an accuracy of 0.80 when only using 5 features. The audio-only KNN model performs very poorly, as does the biosignal mode.

Table 7: Results of 7-way VTE Classification using KNN with SelectKBest

Green values indicate cases where the model accuracy is above 70%, yellow over 60%, and red under 30%, while bolded features indicate the features that were also selected in phonation classification. All the selected video features are from MediaPipe Pose.

Modality	Selected features	F1 score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
All (Mixed Mode)	All	0.6749	0.6736	0.6912	0.6736
All (Mixed Mode)	Right Eye Outer Z, Left Ear Z, Right Ear Z, Mouth Left Z, Right Shoulder Z	0.8029	0.8021	0.8046	0.8021
Audio Only	All	0.2302	0.234	0.2365	0.234
Audio Only	Spectral Centroid, Tristimulus 3, MFCC 1, MFCC 3, MFCC 7	0.1972	0.2013	0.2022	0.2013
Video Only	All	0.9992	0.9992	0.9992	0.9992
Video Only	Right Eye Outer Z, Left Ear Z, Right Ear Z, Mouth Left Z, Right Shoulder Z	0.8029	0.8021	0.8046	0.8021
Biosignal Only	All (raw EMG and PZT)	0.289	0.288	0.3005	0.288

We can see that most of the audio and video features selected change when the task is changed from phonation to VTE classification. However, for audio, MFCC 1 and 3 continue to be selected. Using only 5 video features attains better accuracy than using all the available features. Additionally, when selecting 5 features with SelectKBest, the system selects the same 5 features whether it is selecting from the entire feature set or the video feature set.

Figure 14 shows the confusion matrices for the 7-way error classification of the three different modes when selecting a maximum of 5 features. These further demonstrate

⁵https://github.com/suvimh/vocal_data_feature_based_classification_for_colab

⁶<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1XI2V4NdxogUyX9XMpWv3sD1Y8IZUgRdk?usp=sharing>

how much the audio model struggles in the 7-way KNN classification task compared to video. A 7-way KNN classifier model is not robust enough for crossmodal VTE detection and further experiments focused on testing the suitability of other machine learning algorithms.

Figure 14: Confusion Matrices for VTE KNN classifiers

4.2.2 7-way VTE MLP Classifier

The notebook containing the detailed results of the MLP VTE classifier for Participant 14 can be viewed in Google Colab⁷. As seen in Table 8, MLP improves the performance metrics, especially for the mixed mode classifier using all the available features. However, while the audio model improves with MLP, it only attains about 0.30 accuracy when all 28 audio features are used and improves only a very slight for the model using 5 audio features. There is a slight improvement in the biosignal mode as well. Video continues to outperform the other modalities, although its performance when using 5 features slightly declines.

The same features are selected for classification, whether the entire feature set or only video features are used, as with the KNN model. The same feature selection algorithm is used. Figure 15 shows how VTE classification slightly improves from the KNN, and the VTEs that the model performs well with change from the KNN. However, it is still incomparable to the video modality’s performance.

Figure 15: Confusion Matrices for VTE MLP classifiers

⁷https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1jPr-RE1pjLDcBdMS49HDkBckzCVC_F4n?usp=sharing

Table 8: Results of 7-way VTE Classification using MLP with SelectKBest

Green values indicate cases where the performance improves from the KNN VTE model by more than 5%, yellow by more than 2%, and red a decrease in performance. All the selected video features are from MediaPipe Pose. F1 score is the mean cross-validated F1 score, while accuracy, precision and recall are macro averages.

Modality	Selected features	F1 score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
All (Mixed Mode)	All	0.9980	1.00	1.00	1.00
All (Mixed Mode)	Right Eye Outer Z, Left Ear Z, Right Ear Z, Mouth Left Z, Right Shoulder z	0.7552	0.75	0.75	0.75
Audio Only	All	0.3062	0.31	0.32	0.31
Audio Only	Spectral Centroid, Tristimulus 3, MFCC 1, MFCC 3, MFCC 7	0.2127	0.21	0.23	0.21
Video Only	All	0.9994	1.0	1.0	1.0
Video Only	Right Eye Outer Z, Left Ear Z, Right Ear Z, Mouth Left Z, Right Shoulder z	0.7552	0.75	0.75	0.75
Biosignal Only	All (raw EMG and PZT)	0.3396	0.35	0.39	0.35

4.2.3 7-way VTE Random Forest (RF) Classifier

The notebook containing the detailed results of the RF VTE classifier for Participant 14 can be viewed in Google Colab⁸. As seen in Table 9, RF improves the performance metrics in most of the models. A significant improvement is seen in the audio model using all features, attaining an accuracy of over 50%, while the audio model using only 5 features improves slightly. There is also an improvement in the performance of the video model using only 5 features, attaining an accuracy of 88%, which is higher than either the MLP or KNN models given the same task. There is a slight decline in the performance of the biosignal model when using RF. Using RF improves the audio-based VTE classification, visually represented in Figure 16b. However, video continues to outperform audio in the RF models.

Figure 16: Confusion Matrices for VTE RF Classifiers

⁸https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1WfXAwKsb7S_KKubDhkPG85D8go7Un0Zk?usp=sharing

Table 9: Results of 7-way VTE Classification using RF with SelectKBest

Green values indicate cases where the performance improves from the MLP VTE model by more than 10%, yellow by more than 5%, and red a decrease in performance. All the selected video features are from MediaPipe Pose. F1 score is the mean cross-validated F1 score, while accuracy, precision and recall are macro averages.

Modality	Selected features	F1 score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
All (Mixed Mode)	All	0.9999	1.00	1.00	1.00
All (Mixed Mode)	Right Eye Outer Z, Left Ear Z, Right Ear Z, Mouth Left Z, Right Shoulder Z	0.8687	0.88	0.87	0.87
Audio Only	All	0.5282	0.53	0.53	0.53
Audio Only	Spectral Centroid, Tristimulus 3, MFCC 1, MFCC 3, MFCC 7	0.2912	0.29	0.29	0.29
Video Only	All	0.9999	1.00	1.00	1.00
Video Only	Right Eye Outer Z, Left Ear Z, Right Ear Z, Mouth Left Z, Right Shoulder z	0.8687	0.88	0.87	0.87
Biosignal Only	All (raw EMG and PZT)	0.2885	0.28	0.29	0.28

4.2.4 Feature Selection

To determine which feature selection algorithm is best suited for the task, the audio-based VTE RF classifier was tested with various feature selection algorithms. The detailed results for each of these can be viewed in the same RF VTE Python Notebook within Google Colab⁹. The results of this analysis are summarised in Table 10.

Table 10: Comparative Analysis of 7-Way Audio-Based VTE Classification Using Various Feature Selection Algorithms

Green values indicate cases where the performance improves from the RF model using SelectKBest and red a decrease in performance. F1 score is the mean cross-validated F1 score, while accuracy, precision and recall are macro averages.

Feature Selection Algorithm	Selected features	F1 score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
SelectKBest	Spectral Centroid, Tristimulus 3, MFCC 1, MFCC 3, MFCC 7	0.2912	0.29	0.29	0.29
CFS	MFCC 7, MFCC 8, MFCC 9, MFCC 5, MFCC 4	0.2296	0.23	0.23	0.23
RFE	Pitch, RMS Energy, Tristimulus 2, MFCC 1, MFCC 3	0.4142	0.43	0.43	0.43
RFECV	All	0.5193	0.53	0.53	0.53
PCA	PC1, PC2, PC3, PC4, PC5	0.2835	0.29	0.29	0.29
Permutation importance	MFCC 9, MFCC 5, MFCC 7, Spectral Centroid, MFCC 3	0.2453	0.24	0.24	0.24

RFECV identified using all available features as optimal, making it impractical for real-time applications. Both CFS and permutation importance performed worse

⁹https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1WfXAwKsb7S_KKubDhkPG85D8go7Un0Zk?usp=sharing

than SelectKBest. However, RFE surpassed SelectKBest in the 7-way classification task. While PCA delivered similar classification results to SelectKBest, it compresses the features into a different space, reducing interpretability.

Figure 17: Impact of Feature Count on Accuracy for SelectKBest and RFE in 7-Way VTE Classification Using Random Forest

The variation in classification accuracy with an increasing number of features was examined for both SelectKBest and RFE. The results, shown in Figure 17, indicate that RFE identified feature combinations that achieved higher accuracy with fewer features compared to SelectKBest. The most significant improvement occurred as the number of features increased from 1 to 4, followed by a steady rise. RFE reached 50% accuracy with just 11 features, whereas SelectKBest needed 23 features.

4.2.5 4-way Random Forest VTE Classifier with RFE

The detailed results of the RFE implementation of the 4-way classifiers for Participant 14 can be viewed in the provided Google Colab⁹. The results of the initial 4-way classifications implemented with MLP and RF using SelectKBest for feature selection, which indicated that splitting the VTE classifications into two smaller tasks improved accuracy can be viewed in Appendix E.

A mixed-mode model using audio or video was compared with an audio-only model. As seen in Table 11, the audio-based posture VTE model using RFE improved accuracy by 0.12 from the 7-way model using RFE. The performance of the 4-way models using all audio features also improves from its equivalent 7-way classifier. However, when given the option to select from audio or video features, the system continues to choose only video features for classification. The selected features for the audio-only system vary slightly from the 7-way classification. While Pitch, RMS Energy and MFCC 3 continue to be selected for the 4-way posture classification, Tristimulus 1 and 3 are selected instead of Tristimulus 2 and MFCC 1.

Table 11: 4-way Posture VTE RF Classification Results Using Participant 14’s Data

Green values indicate cases where the performance improves from the RF 7-way VTE model by more than 10%, and yellow by more than 5%, while bolded features indicate which features are the same as selected by RFE in the 7-way classification task. F1 score is the mean cross-validated F1 score, while accuracy, precision and recall are macro averages.

Modality	Selected features	F1 score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
Audio Only	All	0.5990	0.60	0.60	0.60
Audio Only (RFE 5 features)	Pitch, RMS Energy , Tristimulus 1, Tristimulus 3, MFCC 3	0.5314	0.54	0.54	0.54
Audio or Video	All	0.9999	1.00	1.00	1.00
Audio or Video	Right Eye Z, Right Eye Outer Z, Left Ear Z, Right Ear Z, Mouth Left Z	0.9051	0.91	0.91	0.91

As seen in Table 12, the audio-based other VTE model using RFE also improves from the 7-way model, this time by 0.10. The selected features change as the task changes and more audio features correspond to those selected in the 7-way classification model. Pitch, RMS Energy and MFCC 3 were selected in both 4-way classification models. However, MFCC 1 and 5 are selected in the other VTE classification instead of any of the Tristimulus values. However, the accuracies for the crossmodal audio-based VTE detection still remain below 70% when using 5 features selected by RFE in both 4-way splits. Therefore, the final RF implementation splits the task into 6 individual classification tasks.

Table 12: 4-way Other VTE RF Classification Results Using Participant 14’s Data

Green values indicate cases where the performance improves from the RF 7-way VTE model by more than 10%, while bolded features indicate which features are the same as selected by RFE in the 7-way classification task. F1 score is the mean cross-validated F1 score, while accuracy, precision and recall are macro averages.

Modality	Selected features	F1 score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
Audio Only	All	0.6351	0.64	0.64	0.64
Audio Only (RFE 5 features)	Pitch, RMS Energy, MFCC 1, MFCC 3, MFCC 5	0.5136	0.52	0.52	0.52
Audio or Video	All	1.0	1.00	1.00	1.00
Audio or Video	Left Elbow x, Right Elbow Y, Right Wrist Y, Right Hip Y, Left Knee y	0.9950	1.00	1.00	1.00

4.3 Crossmodal VTE Detection

4.3.1 Combined VTE Model

The Python Notebook containing the detailed results of the RF with RFE models for the combined data can be viewed in Google Colab¹⁰. With the aim of minimising

¹⁰https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1ChE1WCVJotVpzYmUcqWZjgfp4KKSJe5E0?usp=drive_link

features used while attaining good results, the results for the models using 5 features are reported below in Table 14, as this value was deemed most suitable. The 2-way VTE RF classifiers using combined data of Participants 14 and 9 yielded accuracies above 70%, as seen in Table 13.

Table 13: Results of 2-way VTE Classifiers using RF with RFE Using Combined Data

Bolded features indicate which features are the same as selected by SelectKBest in the 2-way phonation classification task of the combined data (see Table 4). F1 score, accuracy, precision and recall are macro averages.

Task	Selected features	Accuracy	F1 Score	Precision	Recall
Correct - Hunched Back	Pitch, Spectral Spread, Tristimulus 2, MFCC 1, MFCC 3	0.71	0.71	0.71	0.71
Correct - Arched back	Pitch, RMS Energy , Tristimulus 2, MFCC 1, MFCC 3	0.71	0.71	0.71	0.71
Correct - Sideways Posture	Pitch, RMS Energy, MFCC 1, MFCC 3, MFCC 6	0.69	0.68	0.69	0.68
Correct - High Articulation	Pitch, MFCC 1, MFCC 3, MFCC 4, MFCC 5	0.72	0.72	0.72	0.72
Correct - Low Articulation	Pitch, RMS Energy, MFCC 1, MFCC 3, MFCC 4	0.71	0.71	0.71	0.71
Correct - Chest Breathing	Pitch, RMS Energy, MFCC 1, MFCC 3, MFCC 4	0.70	0.70	0.70	0.70

Across all the different VTEs, 8 unique audio features are used to attain these classification results; Pitch, Spectral Spread, Tristimulus 2, MFCC 1, MFCC 3, MFCC 4, MFCC 5 and MFCC 6. These 8 audio features are used in various combinations of 5 in the different models to accurately classify the data of both participants about 70% of the time. Three of these features correspond to those selected by SelectKBest for the 2-way classification of phonation in the combined data.

4.3.2 Individual VTE Model for Participant 14

The final implementation of six separate VTE RF classifiers for each of the VTEs yielded accuracies above 70% for Participant 14, as seen in Table 14. All individualised models improved performance slightly from the models using combined data. It can be seen that when RFE selects 5 features for each condition, similar results are attained across models. The detailed results of these experiments are visible in Google Colab¹¹.

As can be seen from Table 14, Pitch and RMS Energy continue to be selected throughout almost all the models, largely impacting the classification of each VTE. The High Articulation condition is the only one that does not use RMS Energy for classification. MFCC 1 is selected for the Arched Back, Sideways Posture, High Articulation and Chest Breathing conditions. Across all the different VTEs, 11 unique audio features are used to attain these classification results. How these are

¹¹https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1WfXAwKsb7S_KKubDhkPG85D8go7Un0Zk?usp=sharing

Table 14: Results of 2-way VTE Classifiers using RF with RFE Using Participant 14’s Data

Yellow values indicate cases where the performance improves from the 2-way VTE models using combined data by more than 2%, while bolded features indicate which features are the same as selected by SelectKBest in the 2-way phonation classification task of Participant 14 (see Table 5). F1 score, accuracy, precision and recall are macro averages.

Task	Selected features	Accuracy	F1 Score	Precision	Recall
Correct - Hunched Back	Pitch, RMS Energy , Spectral Slope , Tristimulus 2, Tristimulus 3	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75
Correct - Arched back	Pitch, RMS Energy , Tristimulus 2, MFCC 1 , MFCC 3	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73
Correct - Sideways Posture	Pitch, RMS Energy , Spectral Centroid, Tristimulus 2, MFCC 1	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73
Correct - High Articulation	Pitch, MFCC 1 , MFCC 3 , MFCC 4, MFCC 5	0.74	0.74	0.74	0.74
Correct - Low Articulation	Pitch, RMS Energy , Spectral Centroid, Spectral Slope , Tristimulus 1	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73
Correct - Chest Breathing	Pitch, RMS Energy , MFCC 1 , MFCC 4, MFCC 5	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73

used in combination with one another varies across the conditions. As can be seen from the bolded values in the table, each model shared at least two features with those selected by SelectKBest for the classification of the phonation of Participant 14.

4.3.3 Individual VTE Model for Participant 9

The Python Notebook containing the detailed results of the RF with RFE models for Participant 9 can be viewed in Google Colab¹². This includes the results of the 4-way classification of VTE using the data of Participant 9. The implementation of six separate VTE RF classifiers also yielded accuracies above 70% for Participant 9, as summarised in Table 15 below. When comparing to Table 14, we can see that while some models attain slightly higher or lower accuracies than their counterparts for Participant 14, these values lie in a similar range. However, when comparing to the model using combined data, we can see there is a significant improvement in performance in most cases when Participant 9 is made their individual models. To ensure comparability with prior Tables, Table 15 only shows the results for when 5 features are used.

As can be seen from Table 15, the pitch is selected throughout all the models, similarly to those of Participant 14. MFCC 1 and RMS Energy seem to be an important feature for detecting many of the VTEs of Participant 9 as it was for Participant 14. For Participant 9 MFCC 3 and 4 also seem to play an important role across conditions. Across all the different VTEs, 9 unique audio features are

¹²<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1UCBW3cnogigPMGwtS4QEJAGJ4xjEzUM3?usp=sharing>

Table 15: Results of 2-way VTE Classifiers using RF with RFE Using Participant 9’s Data

Green values indicate cases where the performance improves from the 2-way VTE models using combined data by more than 5%, yellow by 2%, red a decrease, while bolded features indicate which features are the same as selected by SelectKBest in the 2-way phonation classification task of Participant 9 (see Table 6). F1 score, accuracy, precision and recall are macro averages.

Task	Selected features	Accuracy	F1 Score	Precision	Recall
Correct - Hunched Back	Pitch, Spectral Spread, Tristimulus 3, MFCC 1, MFCC 3	0.71	0.70	0.71	0.70
Correct - Arched back	Pitch, RMS Energy, Tristimulus 3, MFCC 1, MFCC 3	0.72	0.72	0.72	0.72
Correct - Sideways Posture	Pitch, Spectral Spread, MFCC 3 , MFCC 4, MFCC 6	0.77	0.76	0.77	0.76
Correct - High Articulation	Pitch, RMS Energy, MFCC 1, MFCC 3, MFCC 4	0.76	0.76	0.77	0.76
Correct - Low Articulation	Pitch, RMS Energy, MFCC 1, MFCC 3, MFCC 4	0.77	0.77	0.77	0.77
Correct - Chest Breathing	Pitch, Spectral Slope , Tristimulus 3, MFCC 3, MFCC 4	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.76

used to attain these classification results; Pitch, RMS Energy, Spectral Spread, Spectral Slope, Tristimulus 3, MFCC 1, MFCC 3, MFCC 4, MFCC 6.

4.3.4 Spectrogram-Based Convolutional Neural Network VTE Model

The Python Notebook of a brief preliminary exploration of spectrogram-based CNN classification of the VTEs can be viewed in Google Colab¹³. Table 16 summarises the results attained from this preliminary exploration. It can be seen that while allowing the models to train for the full 200 epochs significantly increased the accuracy of classifying the training data, the accuracy of classifying the validation and testing data did not improve as much. It should be noted that this was a brief, simple implementation of Spectral-based CNN classification and therefore does not report conclusive results on the suitability of Spectral-based CNNs in this classification task.

Table 16: Results For CNN with Audio Spectrogram Input

Data	Training set accuracy	Validation set accuracy	Test set accuracy	Test set loss
Participant 14	0.7588	0.2917	0.3083	2.4654
Participant 9	0.7119	0.2128	0.2288	2.6619
Combined 14 and 9	0.8187	0.2842	0.2489	4.0766

¹³https://colab.research.google.com/drive/12ngKMGg82c7RRPgKk_U-uJk4FsPWdmKY?usp=sharing

Chapter 5

Discussion and Conclusion

This last chapter briefly summarises the work providing a discussion regarding the implemented methods and the obtained results. Section 5.1 provides the summary and discussion of the data collection and processing, while Section 5.2 evaluates the feature extraction procedures. Section 5.3 provides a discussion of the implemented KNN Phonation classifiers and their results. Section 5.4 compares the performance of the different models experimented with for crossmodal Vocal Technique Error (VTE) detection, while Section 5.5 discusses the performance of the final obtained models for VTE classification. In Section 5.6 we outline possible future work in the field of real-time classification of vocal technique errors and technologies for vocal pedagogical support.

5.1 The Multimodal Vocal Dataset

To extend the scope of research in technologies for vocal pedagogy, we collected a small multimodal dataset incorporating audio, video, and biosignal data to capture expressive resources and mistakes in singing. This dataset includes four different scales sung by 14 participants: 2 professional, 5 intermediate, and 7 inexperienced singers. VTE and phonation labels were manually annotated by the authors. While VTE labels were established during data collection for experienced singers, the data for inexperienced singers currently lacks these labels. Future studies involving vocal experts could label this data and compare it with system-generated labels. Similar work could be done to verify the existing phonation labels and expand the inexperienced data to contain the phonation labels to enhance the dataset.

All recordings were conducted in the same room using 3 different audio sources, 2 video sources, and EMG and PZT sensors for biosignal data. This variety in data sources aims to simulate the diverse recording conditions that users might encounter, ensuring that the dataset supports unbiased development of vocal pedagogy technologies.

Aligning biosignal data with audio and video presented challenges due to variations in timing and potential delays, complicating millisecond-level synchronization. For

example, interpreting EMG data was complicated by jaw movements and swallowing, which weren't always visible in video recordings. Despite these challenges, the dataset was carefully cleaned and aligned to ensure the best possible alignment and provide a reliable basis for further analysis.

The dataset requires additional data, particularly from male voices, to ensure generalizability, as it currently contains more experienced female singers. Additionally, further data collection could involve completing the incomplete data of certain individual participants. However, the inclusion of incomplete data could help explore how general models can be gradually customized for individuals over time.

5.2 Multimodal Feature Extraction

The raw audio and video data were processed algorithmically to develop the dataset so it contains a multimodal feature set. We extracted 28 audio features, 33 body pose landmarks and 68 face landmarks for 30ms non-overlapping windows. The audio features list was based on the work of Girado et al [28], which was used in the development of SkyNote. In this way, the dataset is well prepared for integration with SkyNote in the future.

To enhance the dataset for feature-based classification, it could be beneficial to incorporate the feature set used by Yesiler and Ramirez [29]. While many of these features are unavailable in Essentia, expanding the audio feature extraction could allow us to identify other features that might align better with the specific requirements of each classification task.

Regarding facial analysis, the current use of a separate face detection algorithm seems redundant, as the system predominantly relies on the facial landmarks provided by MediaPipe Pose. Future work could explore the effectiveness of alternative libraries, such as MediaPipe Face Mesh, with a closer camera setup. However, it does seem that detailed facial information is not critical for detecting basic singing errors, suggesting that facial data from pose estimation might suffice for simple vocal pedagogical applications. Finally, additional further work could be carried out to extract higher-level features from the biosignal data.

5.3 Phonation Classification Model

Figure 18 presents the summarised results of the 2-way phonation classifier models. The accuracies of individual models and the combined data model show little variation, indicating that using generalised models is suitable for phonation classification, as expected. Existing literature, such as the work of Yesiler and Ramirez [29] has shown the suitability of generalised phonation classification models. From Figure 18 we also see that audio is effective for phonation classification even with limited features. However, video data significantly outperforms audio in this task. While previous studies, such as those by Ephrat et al. [2], Montesinos et al. [6], Li [7], and Gu et al. [14], have demonstrated that combining audiovisual information improves

performance in speech separation tasks, they do not suggest that video alone would outperform audio-only models.

Our findings indicate that video data, even when processed to exclude landmarks that are not present in all the phonation data points, performs unexpectedly well in classification, including in the combined models. This may be due to confounding variables. Recording sessions were split across different days for the phonation modes. A slight difference in the camera angle could easily confound the results. Expanding the dataset so that phonation modes are recorded in the same session or augmenting the video data could help clarify this.

We can see that even with limited features, video-only outperforms audio-only in phonation classification tasks for the Multimodal Vocal Dataset. However, audio performs well in this task as well, and the performance of the video-only model could be due to confounding variables.

Figure 18: Accuracies of 2-Way Phonation KNN Classifier Models

The dataset showcases the potential for effective phonation mode classification, even in 'wrong' postures or techniques. The SelectKBest algorithm identified four out of five common features for the two female intermediate participants. This suggests that it is suitable to develop generalized phonation classification models, at least for individuals of the same sex and vocal range. Further work should determine if the same audio features remain relevant in more generalized models. While audio features seem to stay consistent for similar voice types, video features vary significantly. This further suggests there could be some confounding variables affecting the result. Nevertheless, video models perform well in the combined data model as well.

The biosignal data reveals variations in laryngeal muscle movement and breathing

between phonation modes, as even raw data can be used as an indicator of phonation for classification. This data could be valuable for further understanding physiological changes during singing, enabling audio and video classifiers to provide insights that facilitate learning. Higher-level features could also be extracted to explore the biological aspects of singing related to different postures and phonation modes.

5.4 Building a System for Crossmodal VTE

Figure 19 summarizes the performance of all models tested in this study. As the mixed-mode model often selects video features for classification, later models are compared as using a single modality at a time despite allowing the model to select from audio or video. For audio models using only five features, each subsequent model showed performance improvements. This was not always the case for the performance of models using data from other modalities. The results show promise for the development of crossmodal VTE detection and showcase the suitability of the dataset in various vocal pedagogy research paths.

We can see that regardless of the model used, the performance of the video-only models outperforms the audio-only model. However, with each iteration of the study, better performance was obtained for the audio-only VTE classifier. Interestingly, we also see that the classification using only Biosignal data also improved as the classification tasks were split into smaller ones.

Figure 19: Accuracies of the VTE Models in this Thesis

While video consistently outperformed audio, the result requires further investigation. Although VTE conditions were typically recorded in the same session, slight changes in camera angle or body position (other than the intentional changes) could have introduced confounding variables. Future work could involve extracting higher-level features from body pose data or augmenting video data to make it robust against camera angle variations. As most music pedagogical applications do not currently use video as an input, should a new system wish to incorporate it, developing a proper understanding of the video classifiers is essential. Alternately,

as camera configuration poses many challenges and camera input poses more user privacy issues, it might be better to focus on improving the audio-based crossmodal VTE detection regardless of the efficacy of video.

Separating error conditions into six smaller models significantly improved the performance of audio-only classifiers, achieving final results above 70%. However, it's important to note that these results are based on two intermediate female singers, and the emulated VTE conditions were exaggerated. While vocal coaches confirmed that extreme cases can occur, most individuals may not exhibit such clear problems, especially regarding posture. Therefore, it is crucial to further test these models using data with smaller variations, for example, the beginner data, and validate classifications with an experienced vocal pedagogy researcher or coach.

With further refinement of model parameters, feature selection, and testing different models, more accurate detection of posture and other error conditions from audio alone might be achievable. Increasing the number of features improved model performance, but finding the right balance between feature quantity and real-time performance requires more investigation.

The models performed better as the classification tasks became more focused. Results show that implementing six 2-way error condition classifiers is more effective than larger 7-way or 4-way models. However, since the goal is to integrate these models into a real-time application, further research is needed to determine the best approach for real-time tasks.

Random Forest (RF) worked well for audio and video classification but not for biosignal data, likely due to the limited number of features in the current data. Meanwhile, the MLP model seemed better suited for crossmodal detection based on raw biosignal data. The 2-way RF classification models yielded better results. Higher-level features derived from the raw data might improve performance and using an MLP with less classes could also improve the biosignal models performance. However, as most users would not have access to specialised sensors, instead of using the biosignal data for classification in an application, it would be more beneficial to analyse the biosignal data to understand the internal physical aspects of singing. This can then be further investigated to define what audio signal characteristics correlate with these biological activities so that a system can provide feedback on laryngeal muscle activity and breathing to its users.

5.5 VTE Classification Model

This study has demonstrated significant potential in developing crossmodal VTE classifiers using machine learning, which could be integrated into applications for vocal pedagogical support. The findings align with Luck and Toiviainen's research, suggesting a relationship between a singer's posture and specific vocal performance qualities. The performance of the VTE models is summarized in Figure 20, showing that individual models and combined models generally achieve similar performance in VTE classification. Notable differences occur primarily between the individual

models for Participant 9 and the combined model, especially for Sideways Posture and Low Articulation VTEs.

We can see that all the variations of 2-way models for VTE classification tasks for the Multimodal Vocal Dataset obtain similar results. These results show promise in developing models for real-time VTE classification.

Figure 20: Accuracies of 2-Way VTE Models RF Classifiers with RFE

Across the two individual models, 13 of the 28 audio features were selected in various combinations. However, the combined models achieved sufficient performance using just 8 unique audio features: Pitch, Spectral Spread, Tristimulus 2, and MFCCs 1, 3, 4, 5, and 6. These features, particularly Pitch, RMS energy, Tristimulus, and lower MFCC values, appear to significantly influence the classification results for the VTEs.

Since the current models focus on female singers with similar vocal ranges, further investigation is needed to determine if these features are consistently selected for different voice types when using the entire dataset. This will help identify which features are most relevant for detecting VTEs across various voice types. The need for multiple smaller, individual models tailored to provide better feedback on each user's voice can be expected, given the unique nature of each person's physiology and voice. However, it is rewarding to see that there is potential for developing generalised models for VTEs as well as phonation, as long as the VTE classification models are suitably developed. Further work should complete the analysis with the full dataset.

The 2-way RF classifiers implemented in this study significantly outperformed the preliminary CNN spectrogram models, which are not displayed in Figure 20 as the

CNNs tested were simple and not optimized. Neural networks require large datasets, and the limited data used here was likely insufficient for conclusive results. Further research should focus on identifying the optimal neural network architecture and parameters. Expanding the dataset to include more voice types and augmenting the data with audio from other microphone sources would also be beneficial.

However, this study confirmed that the problem is not easily solvable with a simple neural network, validating the proposed crossmodal error detection approach using feature-based machine learning classifiers. The gradual improvement in model accuracy throughout this exploration indicates strong potential for developing a system capable of crossmodal identification of vocal technique issues.

5.6 Future Research and Development

The following areas offer potential avenues for further research based on this thesis and the created dataset:

- Fine-tune parameters and feature selection for the existing models.
- Augment the dataset by applying effects to expand the existing data.
- Analyze biosignal data across different conditions to provide feedback aligned with the corresponding audio. PZT data can be analyzed to determine breathing rates, amplitudes, and cycles. EMG data can be analyzed to determine how the laryngeal muscle activity changes in different VTE phonation modes, which can be then used to provide information to the user about their laryngeal motion based on other modes.
- Continue investigating spectrum-based CNNs for classifying vocal pedagogical error conditions.
- Explore alternate machine learning and neural network models for classifying vocal pedagogical error conditions.
- Test existing models on beginner singers' data to evaluate their effectiveness in capturing errors and manually validate the results.
- Implement existing models in a real-time application and compare the performance of different classifiers in real-world scenarios.
- Investigate the impact of alternate microphone sources on model performance. While the current models were trained using computer video and audio sources (as they align with Skynote's primary input), future research should analyze the other input sources.

5.7 Conclusion

In this study, we extend the scope of research in vocal pedagogical technologies, by developing a small multimodal dataset incorporating audio, video, and biosignal data to capture expressive resources and vocal technique errors (VTEs) in singing. This study shows there is potential in using pure audio signals for classifying vocal pedagogical errors, despite video consistently outperforming audio in the classification tasks investigated. Biosignal analysis offers valuable insights for voice technologies, but audio and video should remain primary input sources for any vocal pedagogical application. Machine learning shows promise in identifying both phonation and VTEs, which can be leveraged to enhance vocal pedagogy, providing feedback on voice quality, posture, breathing, articulation, and phonation.

Further research is required to explore the feasibility of developing a generalised system based on key features, which can then personalise its feedback as a user's voice data is incorporated. Such a system could offer initial guidance, gradually refining its feedback as it adapts to the unique characteristics of each user. We envision a future where a system begins with a generalised model to support beginners, and with input from vocal coaches, evolves to provide increasingly tailored feedback that enhances the learning process.

Appendix A contains all the necessary links to the code required to reproduce our experiments.

Bibliography

- [1] Reed, C. N. Imagining sensing: Understanding and extending the vocalist-voice relationship through biosignal feedback (2023). URL <https://qmro.qmul.ac.uk/xmlui/handle/123456789/89579>.
- [2] Ephrat, A. et al. Looking to listen at the cocktail party: A speaker-independent audio-visual model for speech separation. ACM Transactions on Graphics **37**, 11 (2018). URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/1804.03619v2>.
- [3] Gao, R. & Grauman, K. Visualvoice: Audio-visual speech separation with cross-modal consistency. Proc. IEEE Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit. 15490–15500 (2021). URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2101.03149v2>.
- [4] Nguyen, V. N., Sadeghi, M., Ricci, E. & Alameda-Pineda, X. Deep variational generative models for audio-visual speech separation. IEEE International Workshop on Machine Learning for Signal Processing, MLSP 2021-October (2020). URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2008.07191v2>.
- [5] Wu, J. et al. Time domain audio visual speech separation. 2019 IEEE Automatic Speech Recognition and Understanding Workshop (ASRU 2019) 667–673 (2019). URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/1904.03760v2>.
- [6] Montesinos, J. F., Kadandale, V. S. & Haro, G. A cappella: Audio-visual singing voice separation (2021). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2104.09946>.
- [7] Li, B. Multi-modal analysis for music performances (2020). URL <https://www.proquest.com/openview/efe74006d04d4dc1b94cd0b83a634d24/1.pdf?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=2026366&diss=y>.
- [8] Michelsanti, D. et al. An overview of deep-learning-based audio-visual speech enhancement and separation. IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio Speech and Language Processing **29**, 1368–1396 (2020). URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2008.09586v2>.
- [9] Skynote - mtg - music technology group (upf). URL https://www.upf.edu/web/mtg/finished-projects/-/asset_publisher/0xmt1Lu0pYtH/content/skynote/maximized.
- [10] Deng, Z. & Zhou, R. Vocal92: Multimodal audio dataset with a cappella solo singing and speech. IEEE Access **11**, 140958–140966 (2023). URL https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369042871_Vocal92_Multimodal_Audio_Dataset_with_a_Cappella_Solo_Singing_and_Speech.

- [11] Sundberg, J. *The science of the singing voice* (Northern Illinois University Press, 1987). URL https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Science_of_the_Singing_Voice.html?id=iYGNQgAACAAJ.
- [12] Toiviainen, P. & Luck, G. Ideal singing posture: evidence from behavioural studies and computational motion analysis ideal singing posture: Evidence from behavioral studies and computational motion analysis (2007). URL https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228371312_Ideal_singing_posture_evidence_from_behavioural_studies_and_computational_motion_analysis.
- [13] Stoller, D. & Dixon, S. Analysis and classification of phonation modes in singing. *17th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference* (2016). URL <https://qmro.qmul.ac.uk/xmlui/handle/123456789/13500>.
- [14] Gu, X., Zeng, W., Zhang, J., Ou, L. & Wang, Y. Deep audio-visual singing voice transcription based on self-supervised learning models (2023). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2304.12082>.
- [15] Clayton, M., Rao, P., Shikarpur, N., Roychowdhury, S. & Li, J. Raga classification from vocal performances using multimodal analysis (2022). URL <https://dap-lab.github.io/multimodal-raga-supplementary/>.
- [16] Chowdhury, A., Cozzo, A. & Ross, A. Jukebox: A multilingual singer recognition dataset (2020). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2008.03507>.
- [17] Wilkins, J., Seetharaman, P., Wahl, A. & Pardo, B. Vocalset: A singing voice dataset. *19th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference* (2018). URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1203819>.
- [18] Bertin-Mahieux, T., Ellis, D. P. W., Whitman, B. & Lamere, P. The million song dataset (2011). URL <http://millionsongdataset.com/>.
- [19] Mehrabani, M. & Hansen, J. H. L. Singing speaker clustering based on subspace learning in the gmm mean supervector space (2013). URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.specom.2012.11.001>.
- [20] Xulong, Z. artist 20 the public dataset from labrosa (2019). URL <http://labrosa.ee.columbia.edu/projects/artistid/>.
- [21] Black, D., A., A., Li, M., Mi. & Tian. Singing voice audio dataset (2014). URL <http://isophonics.net/SingingVoiceDataset>.
- [22] Li, B. University of rochester audio-visual solo singing performance (ursing) dataset (2020). URL <https://zenodo.org/records/6404999>.
- [23] Proutskova, P., Rhodes, C., Wiggins, G. & Crawford, T. Breathy or resonant – a controlled and curated dataset for phonation mode detection in singing (2012). URL <https://research.gold.ac.uk/id/eprint/9796/>.
- [24] Pernollet, M. vocobox/human-voice-dataset: Human voice wave samples (2014). URL <https://github.com/vocobox/human-voice-dataset>.
- [25] Gu, X., Ou, L., Ong, D. & Wang, Y. Mm-alt: A multimodal automatic lyric transcription system (2022). URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/3503161.3548411>.

- [26] Thorpe, W. & Doorn, J. V. The science of singing and seeing (2004). URL <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228882200>.
- [27] Georgaki, A., Kouroupetroglou, G. & Moschos, F. Fonaskein: An interactive software application for the practice of the singing voice (2016). URL <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/308031033>.
- [28] Giraldo, S. et al. Automatic assessment of tone quality in violin music performance. *Frontiers in Psychology* **10** (2019). URL <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychology/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.00334/full>.
- [29] Yesiler, F. & Ramirez, R. A machine learning approach to classification of phonation modes in singing. URL https://web.archive.org/web/20200302112216/https://zenodo.org/record/1422611/files/smc_2018_050.pdf.
- [30] Homepage — essentia 2.1-beta6-dev documentation. URL <https://essentia.upf.edu/index.html>.
- [31] Chung, J. L., Ong, L. Y. & Leow, M. C. Comparative analysis of skeleton-based human pose estimation. *Future Internet* **14** (2022). URL <https://www.mdpi.com/1999-5903/14/12/380>.
- [32] Opencv - open computer vision library. URL <https://opencv.org/>.
- [33] dlib c++ library. URL <http://dlib.net/>.
- [34] Openface. URL <https://cmusatyalab.github.io/openface/>.
- [35] Face landmark detection guide | google ai edge | google ai for developers. URL https://ai.google.dev/edge/mediapipe/solutions/vision/face_landmarker.
- [36] Savin, A. V., Sablina, V. A. & Nikiforov, M. B. Comparison of facial landmark detection methods for micro-expressions analysis (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc., 2021). URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9460191>.
- [37] Plux biosignals. URL <https://www.pluxbiosignals.com/>.
- [38] biosignalsplux. Electromyography (emg) sensor data sheet muscle (2017). URL <https://support.pluxbiosignals.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/biosignalsplux-Electromyography-EMG-Datasheet.pdf>.
- [39] biosignalsplux. Respiration (pzt) sensor datasheet (2020). URL https://support.pluxbiosignals.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/Respiration_PZT_Datasheet.pdf.
- [40] biosignalsplux. Respiration (pzt) sensor user manual (2020). URL https://support.pluxbiosignals.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/Respiration_PZT_User_Manual.pdf.
- [41] biosignalsplux. Electromyography (emg) sensor user manual (2020). URL <https://support.pluxbiosignals.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/biosignalsplux-Electromyography-EMG-User-Manual-1.pdf>.

- [42] Kim, J. W., Salamon, J., Li, P. & Bello, J. P. Crepe: A convolutional representation for pitch estimation (2018). URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/1802.06182>. 1802.06182.
- [43] Yesiler, F. & Ramirez, R. Master thesis on sound and music computing analysis and automatic classification of phonation modes in singing (2018). URL <https://zenodo.org/records/1468229>.
- [44] Lee, H., Pham, P., Largman, Y. & Ng, A. Unsupervised feature learning for audio classification using convolutional deep belief networks. 1096–1104 (2009). URL https://www.researchgate.net/publication/221619818_Unsupervised_feature_learning_for_audio_classification_using_convolutional_deep_belief_networks.
- [45] Costa, Y., de Oliveira, L. & Silla, C. An evaluation of convolutional neural networks for music classification using spectrograms. *Applied Soft Computing* **52** (2017). URL https://www.researchgate.net/publication/311650413_An_Evaluation_of_Convolutional_Neural_Networks_for_Music_Classification_Using_Spectrograms.
- [46] KNeighborsClassifier — scikit-learn 1.5.1 documentation. URL <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.neighbors.KNeighborsClassifier.html>.
- [47] MLPClassifier — scikit-learn 1.5.1 documentation. URL https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.neural_network.MLPClassifier.html.
- [48] RandomForestClassifier — scikit-learn 1.5.1 documentation. URL <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.ensemble.RandomForestClassifier.html>.
- [49] The sequential model. URL https://keras.io/guides/sequential_model/.
- [50] SelectKBest — scikit-learn 1.5.1 documentation. URL https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.feature_selection.SelectKBest.html.
- [51] Sahazada, S. Correlation-based feature selection in a data science project | by sariq sahadada | medium (2023). URL <https://medium.com/@sariq16/correlation-based-feature-selection-in-a-data-science-project-3ca08d2af5c6>.
- [52] Rfe — scikit-learn 1.5.1 documentation. URL https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.feature_selection.RFE.html.
- [53] Rfecn — scikit-learn 1.5.1 documentation. URL https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.feature_selection.RFECV.html.
- [54] Pca — scikit-learn 1.5.1 documentation. URL <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.decomposition.PCA.html>.
- [55] permutation_importance — scikit-learn 1.5.1 documentation. URL https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.inspection.permutation_importance.html.

Appendices

Appendix A

Links for Reproducing the Work

To contribute to the Open Science movement and support future research of technologies for vocal pedagogy, all the resources used in this thesis are publicly accessible. The links required to reproduce all the work of the thesis are collected below. Note that the provided links for the specific Colab Notebooks are intended for viewing and are connected to the Google Drive of whoever is using them. Therefore the files containing the scripts, etc. must be also copied if running these notebooks and filepaths should be updated accordingly.

Code for Cleaning Data

https://github.com/suvimh/vocal_data_cleaning

Code for Feature Extraction

https://github.com/suvimh/vocal_data_feature_extraction

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1n0oCDDvmJ6Y0GNAAFF7UNw-SH2JxeegB?usp=sharing>

Code for All Classification Models

https://github.com/suvimh/vocal_data_feature_based_classification_for_colab

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1gX4fMXhi32mpUk2z7-yEH6NWgBUIGKls?usp=sharing>

Appendix B

Experiment to Verify Electromyography (EMG) Sensor Placement

The placement of the EMG sensors was tested to confirm that the outputted data reflected the findings in Reed's thesis [1]. To ensure that the EMG sensor placement was satisfactory, a short sequence of tests was performed to verify detectable changes in the sensor recordings during singing. The first of these showed that there was a clear difference in the sensor data output when not singing and when singing, as shown in Figure 21.

To ensure that the change wasn't simply due to jaw movement, a simple siren exercise was conducted where the mouth was kept shut and a hummed pitch was changed. There was a visible increase in the EMG sensor output when doing this, as seen in Figure 22. The test showed that the activity of the laryngeal muscles increases at both extremes of the vocal range, which aligns with the physiological theory.

Figure 21: Data Output When Singing the Exercise 'ngi-nge-nga-o-u'

Based on this preliminary testing, it was confirmed that the EMG sensor was a valuable data source for the project. The preliminary testing also informed the pro-

Figure 22: Data Output When Singing a Siren Exercise

cedures for finding the correct EMG positioning on participants and how to monitor the placement's appropriateness by reading the resulting graphs. This was a crucial first step to ensure data quality. To account for individual physical differences, a consistent procedure for finding a suitable sensor placement was developed. These tests also highlighted the importance of only analyzing the data during moments of singing, as touching the sensors or significant movements could introduce noise into the signal.

Appendix C

Evaluating the Suitability of FLD Libraries

Four FLD implementations were assessed using a test video clip from the collected data featuring a subject with a turned-away face. OpenFace was excluded from testing due to the setup describing it requiring Python 2.7 [34], while the project was already being developed in Python 3.11 and feature extraction was developed in 3.10. Since OpenFace is based on dlib and OpenCV, testing was focused on the original libraries instead. Also, a combined approach using OpenCV and dlib was tested. A Python Jupyter Notebook, available on GitHub¹ was developed to facilitate the testing of the face and pose libraries.

(a) On this frame of video, OpenCV doesn't display clear landmarks, Mediapipe overlays the face in the wrong position, the combined implementation doesn't track the face and dlib tracks face correctly

(b) On another frame of video, OpenCV still doesn't display clear landmarks, while Mediapipe doesn't track the face, the both the combined implementation performs well and the pure dlib implementation tracks the face correctly

Figure 23: Screen Shots from Qualitative FLD Assessment (Top Left: Open CV, Top Right: MediaPipe Face Mesh, Bottom Left: Combined OpenCV and dlib, Bottom right: dlib)

A qualitative assessment of each implementation's proficiency in generating face landmarks from the test video is summarized in Figures 23a and 23b. MediaPipe

¹https://github.com/suvimh/pose_face_testing

encountered significant challenges when participants were positioned at a further distance from the camera, although it was feasible to capture the face mesh when participants went through a configuration step. However, the tracking was lost if participants turned their heads. In such instances, MediaPipe often failed to display any facial landmarks on the video feed, occasionally attempting to overlay an oversized face mesh onto the image, as illustrated in the top right corner of Figure 23a. The pure OpenCV implementation did not output clear landmark outputs, making performance analysis difficult: It also occasionally resulted in the loss of face detection. The combined implementation utilizing both OpenCV and dlib demonstrated comparable performance to that of the pure dlib implementation, but dropped the landmarks in some frames, while the pure dlib seemed more stable.

Appendix D

MediaPipe Pose Landmarks

Table 17 shows the placement of the Mediapipe Pose landmarks on the human body, attained from the documentation¹. This table can be used as a reference when looking at the provided Python Notebooks, as the landmarks outputted by the code as the numerical values rather than the location names.

Table 17: Mediapipe HPE landmark locations

0 nose	1 left eye (inner)	2 left eye	3 left eye (outer)	4 right eye (inner)	5 right eye	6 right eye (outer)	7 left ear	8 right ear
9 mouth (left)	10 mouth (right)	11 left shoulder	12 right shoulder	13 left elbow	14 right elbow	15 left wrist	16 right wrist	17 left pinky
18 right pinky	19 left index	20 right index	21 left thumb	22 right thumb	23 left hip	24 right hip	25 left knee	26 right knee
27 left ankle	28 right ankle	29 left heel	30 right heel	31 left foot index	32 right foot index			

¹Pose landmark detection guide | Google AI Edge | Google AI for Developers. (n.d.). Retrieved February 24, 2024, from https://ai.google.dev/edge/mediapipe/solutions/vision/pose_landmarker

Appendix E

Alternate 4-way Classification Models

E.1 4-way MLP VTE Classifiers with SelectKBest

4-way Posture VTE Classification with MLP

To investigate whether the MLP would perform better when handling smaller classification tasks, the 7-way classification was split into two 4-way classification tasks. Table 18 and Figure ?? display the results for the classifier handling the various posture-related issues present in the data.

Table 18: Summary of Posture MLP Classification Results

Modality	Selected features	Mean cross-validated F1 score	Average Accuracy	Average Precision (macro)	Average Recall (macro)
Audio Only	All	0.4333	0.45	0.45	0.45
Audio Only	Spectral Centroid Spectral slope, Spectral Decrease, MFCC 1, MFCC 10	0.2935	0.31	0.31	0.31
Video or Audio	All	0.9993	1.0	1.0	1.0
Video or Audio	right eye z, right eye outer z, left ear z, right ear z, mouth left z	0.8419	0.85	0.85	0.85

While using all the audio features in the MLP for posture classification attains 45% accuracy, video significantly outperforms audio in this classification task.

4-way Other VTE Classification with MLP

Table 19 displays the results for the classifier handling the non-posture issues present in the data.

When separating the non-posture-related error conditions, the performance of the audio-only mode improves slightly. While using all the audio features in the MLP for posture classification attains 49% accuracy, video still outperforms audio.

Table 19: Summary of Other VTE MLP Classification Results

Modality	Selected features	Mean cross-validated F1 score	Average Accuracy	Average Precision (macro)	Average Recall (macro)
Audio Only	All	0.4906	0.49	0.51	0.49
Audio Only	tristimulus1, tristimulus3, MFCC 3, MFCC 7, MFCC 9	0.3325	0.34	0.35	0.35
Video or Audio	All	0.9995	1.0	1.0	1.0
Video or Audio	left elbow x, right elbow y, right wrist y, right hip y, left knee y	0.9348	0.93	0.93	0.93

E.2 Random Forest 4-way VTE Classifiers with SelectKBest

4-way Posture VTE Classification with RF

Table 20: Summary of Posture RF Classification Results

Modality	Selected features	Mean cross-validated F1 score	Average Accuracy	Average Precision (macro)	Average Recall (macro)
Audio Only	All	0.5990	0.60	0.60	0.60
Audio Only	Spectral Centroid Spectral slope, Spectral Decrease, MFCC 1, MFCC 10	0.3466	0.35	0.35	0.35
Video or Audio	All	0.9999	1.00	1.00	1.00
Video or Audio	right eye z, right eye outer z, left ear z, right ear z, mouth left z	0.9051	0.91	0.91	0.91

When splitting the task into a 4-way RF classification of posture conditions, using all audio features attains an accuracy of 0.60. However, the results using only the top 5 features selected by SelectKBest are not comparable to the performance of the video input, as seen in Figure 24 and Table 20. The selected audio features and video features changed from the 7-way classification, as seen when comparing Tables 9 and 20.

Figure 24: Confusion Matrices for 4-way Posture VTE Classifications Using an RF Classifier

Table 21: Summary of Other Error Condition RF Classification Results

Modality	Selected features	Mean cross-validated F1 score	Average Accuracy	Average Precision (macro)	Average Recall (macro)
Audio Only	All	0.6351	0.64	0.64	0.64
Audio Only	tristimulus1, tristimulus3, MFCC 3, MFCC 7, MFCC 9	0.3875	0.39	0.39	0.39
Video or Audio	All	0.9950	1.00	1.00	1.00
Video or Audio	left elbow x, right elbow y, right wrist y, right hip y, left knee y	0.9950	1.00	1.00	1.00

4-way Other VTE Classification with RF

Figure 25: Confusion Matrices for 4-way Other VTE condition Classifications Using an RF Classifier

When splitting the task into a 4-way RF Other VTE classification, using all audio features attains an accuracy of 0.64. RF attains higher accuracy than MLP. However, the results using only the top 5 features selected by SelectKBest are not comparable to the performance of the video input, as seen in Figure 24 and Table 20.